

D8.7 < Progress report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign >

WP8

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Executive Summary

This deliverable D8.7 “Progress report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign” presents overview of performed dissemination and networking activities towards spreading project awareness among stakeholders and public workshop organization for EnDurCrete project up to month M24. This report is a follow up of the deliverable D8.2 “Communication, networking and dissemination plan” in the framework of the EnDurCrete project, dedicated to task T8.1 “Dissemination, Communication and Networking” under the work package WP8 “Training, dissemination and exploitation”. At the end of the project, this report will result to the deliverable D8.11 “Final report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign”. This document was compiled by FENIX and all partners provided their contributions, especially in the frame of dissemination events and activities performed and planned within the EnDurCrete project.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

[D]	Deliverable
[EC]	European Commission
[ECTP]	European Construction Technology Platform
[EU]	European Union
[GDPR]	General Data Protection Regulation
[LCA]	Life Cycle Analysis
[M]	Month
[WP]	Work Package
[T]	Task
[PU]	Public
[CO]	Confidential
[R&D]	Research and Development
[IPR]	Intellectual Property Right
[ECCREDI]	European Council for Construction Research, Development and Innovation
[FIEC]	European Construction Industry Federation

1 Introduction

All dissemination and communication activities are tracked under the EnDurCrete Communication, Networking and Dissemination Plan, which was created at the very beginning of the project. The objective of the Communication, Networking and Dissemination Plan is to identify and organize the activities in order to disseminate of knowledge from the EnDurCrete project and promote the commercial exploitation of the project’s results. The Plan is expanded in two directions: towards the marketing activities in order to enhance the commercial potential of the technology and towards the notification of project results in the scientific, EC and general R&D sector. The Plan summarizes the consortium’s strategy and concrete actions to disseminate and communicate the results generated by the EnDurCrete project. This deliverable D8.7 “Progress report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign” summarizes all activities performed for the EnDurCrete project up to month M24. This report is dependent also on the deliverable D8.4 "Initial Data Management Plan" which identifies the results that should be object of dissemination and exploitation and analyses the main data uses, users and explore the restrictions related to IPR according with the Consortium Agreement. An overview of dissemination opportunities was identified through traditional channels such as event attendance and organization (e.g. conferences, seminars, workshops, fairs, etc.), project publications (e.g. brochures, posters, press releases as well as conference papers, articles in professional journals, etc.) and project presentations, complemented also by online activities based around the project website, newsletter, and through the main social network profiles. The dissemination activities were designed to target the key audiences and stakeholders and to maximize awareness of the EnDurCrete project and its results. Purpose of dissemination is described on graphic below (Figure 1).

Figure 1: EnDurCrete dissemination purpose

2 Obligation to disseminate the project results

As stated in EnDurCrete Grant Agreement article 29, unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must - as soon as possible - disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific publications.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries - unless agreed otherwise - at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within - unless agreed otherwise - 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may - under certain conditions - need to formally notify the Commission before dissemination takes place. Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication—via the repository—at the latest:

- i. on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
- ii. within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym (“New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications”) and grant agreement number (“760639”);
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

3 Communication and dissemination strategy

One of the main goals of WP8 is to reach the widest dissemination of the results generated by the EnDurCrete project and raise public awareness regarding its technology (long lasting reinforced concrete). In this framework, a strong communication strategy was set up in order to reach the target impact to the best. The whole EnDurCrete consortium committed to perform dissemination activities and proactively look for dissemination opportunities. Communication activities aim at creating a common project visual identity and public image, to raise basic interest in the proposed technology and processes, to provide an up-to-date information about the project, to translate the scientific/technical results into messages that can be read by a wide public.

The dissemination strategy consists of the following steps:

- Generation of high-value data and information on technological developments for high-quality communication tools (see chapter 3.3) with the objectives to inform stakeholder groups and to generate interest in the potential replication of the activities.
- Use of the developed tools to communicate with all the relevant stakeholder groups at different stages of technology development and to adjust communication activities and tools on the basis of the role covered by each stakeholder group in the commercialisation and replication of products and services.
- Engagement of the selected target groups to support the uptake of technologies. This step includes actively interacting with e.g. pre-cast and ready-mix concrete manufacturing-related sectors and networking with relevant stakeholders.

3.1 Target audience and stakeholders

The project's dissemination and communication activities are focused on targeting the construction sector in general, community working on durability, positive environmental impact, cost effectiveness. Target groups are all players involved in construction industry and renovation projects:

- Industries, universities and research institutions investigating durability and sustainability issues in pre-cast and cast-in place concrete systems;
- Potential customers in the target sectors: pre-cast and ready-mix concrete markets and manufacturers of new concrete technologies (e.g. anti-corrosion or self-monitoring systems);
- Recommendations and standardisation experts;
- End-users connected to any of the four demonstration sites (i.e. tunnels, offshore structures, harbours, and bridges), or to the use of concrete under critical conditions in general (e.g. industrial building).

The role of the target groups is to give feedback on on-going and foreseen development activities, bring useful inputs related to research findings, existing tools, best practices and market evolution, to help to define the market needs. A stakeholder can be anyone who has an interest in the project

or is affected by its outcomes. Stakeholders for EnDurCrete project were identified and assessed in terms of their interest in the project and the importance for its success and further dissemination.

3.2 Key message

Key messages that the EnDurCrete project wants to give to the targeted audience and stakeholders were defined, following the communication principles as shown on the graphic below (Figure 2). Key messages were agreed between partners and are demonstrated through the project website, brochure, flyer, poster, newsletter, video, etc.

3.3 Tools

Dissemination activities are targeted both nationally and internationally. The tools that are used for dissemination and communication are the following:

- Publications (scientific, technical and economical journals, popular magazines, newspapers)
- Conferences, congresses, workshops, seminars, forums participation
- Fairs, exhibitions participation
- Public workshops, webinars organization
- Press releases
- Internet (project website, social network profiles, thematic portals)
- Links to other projects, clustering activities
- Common visual identity, logo, brochure, poster, project presentation
- Video production (project promo videos, videos from the events, training videos)
- E-newsletters, info graphics
- Gadgets for promotion
- Training sessions, etc.

Figure 2: EnDurCrete Key messages

3.4 Commitment of project partners

EnDurCrete partners with enough man-months (see GA) involved in dissemination proactively participate in communication and dissemination activities related to the project by exploiting their communication channels to reach the widest audience performed in a structured way, and all these activities are tracked on regular basis. Each dissemination activity is carried out by the partner who is the most expert in each specific area, taking into account language knowledge of the targeted

audience. For the tracking of the actions executed by EnDurCrete partners, a set of tools for collection of inputs regarding performed and planned activities has been developed (Figure 3):

- List of scientific publications - Table 1
- List of dissemination events and activities - Table 2a
- Detailed description of events already performed - Table 2b

Each partner is required every six months to provide updated information about dissemination events and communication activities performed and planned by his organization. Partners need to provide to the dissemination leader (FENIX) proofs about events participation (photos, agendas, presentations, videos, etc.) and also detailed information about the events (date, place, target audience, size of audience, type of dissemination such as ppt, brochure, poster, booth, etc.). Project partners are also requested to provide updates about the project progress and achievements for the EnDurCrete website and promo materials to be kept up to date.

Table 1: List of publications														
Publication title	Link	Publication type	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Periodical name/ Publisher	Number, Date	Place	Relevant page	Public & private participative	Peer/revision	Open access	Partner/s	Status
<small>Title of the article</small>	<small>Website link if applicable</small>	<small>(paper in conference, article in journal, books/monographs, chapters in books, thesis, etc.)</small>	<small>Digital Object Identifier</small>	<small>Number</small>	<small>Full names of the authors</small>	<small>Or equivalent</small>	<small>of journal</small>	<small>of publication</small>	<small>of article</small>	<small>YES/NO</small>	<small>YES/NO</small>	<small>YES (green, gold)/NO</small>	<small>As in GA</small>	<small>(Performed/ Planned)</small>

Table 2a: List of dissemination events and activities										
Type of event/activity	Link	Event/activity title	Objective	Date	Place	Partner contribution	Countries addressed	Target audience and size	Partner/s	Status
<small>Conference, fair, workshop, social media, website, thematic portal, press release, newsletter, etc.</small>	<small>Website link if applicable</small>	<small>Official title of the event/activity description</small>	<small>Reason why participated/organized event/performed activity</small>	<small>Date of the event/activity performed</small>	<small>Place of the event/activity</small>	<small>(speech, ppt, poster, brochure, stand, etc.)</small>	<small>(national/international)</small>	<small>Scientific community, industry, HVAC, ESCOs, etc.</small>	<small>As in GA</small>	<small>(Performed/ Planned)</small>

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed				
Event title	Location	Date	Type of event	Responsible partner
Website				
Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)				

Figure 3: Templates for dissemination activities, events and publications tracking

3.5 Evaluation

Dissemination and communication activities are targeted and can be more or less successful. To find out if the dissemination and communication strategy was well chosen and well implemented, it is important to build an evaluation table into all major dissemination and communication activities to monitor the quality and to see if they have achieved their aims. Some key performance indicators have been defined and evaluated up to month M24 as the table below shows.

Table 1: EnDurCrete success Key Performance Indicators

Channel	Description	Success indicator (end of project)	Success indicator (M24)
Project website	Public website providing all relevant project information (project objectives, partners, public deliverables, publications, press releases, news and events, promo materials, social network profiles links, newsletter subscription).	> 20 000 views > 5 000 users	14 545 views 1 933 users
Promo material	Project brochure, roll-up poster, project presentation, updated based on the project development. Downloads from project website.	> 500 downloads > 3 000 printing	1 798 downloads 1 700 printed
Social media campaign	LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube.	> 500 followers in total > 5 000 impressions	257 followers 59 811 impressions
Project videos	Graphical video created at the beginning of project. When the system is developed interview with key partners will take place in order to create project promo video.	> 500 views all videos together > 10 subscribers	613 views 9 subscribers
e-newsletter	An e-mail newsletter created and distributed at six-months interval to identified stakeholders and subscribers.	> 300 subscribers + downloads	3 newsletters released 780 subscribers + downloads
Training activities	Courses and training materials will be provided in order to share and transfer the know-how to the relevant stakeholder communities.	> 6 training sessions > 50 attendees	0

Publication	Consortium partners publish (according to the IPR protection strategy) the results in the scientific literature, dedicated journals and magazines in the field of concrete, industry, new technologies etc. Open Access to peer-reviewed scientific publications provided.	> 5 scientific papers submitted > 5 articles in magazines published	- 1 publication in journal - 5 magazine publication - 2 bachelor theses - 1 chapter in book - 1 project work
Events organization	Final public workshop organization.	> 1 public workshop > 150 participants	- 3 public workshops organization jointly with other projects - 220 participants
Events participation	Project presentation in a number of national and international events (conferences, fairs, seminars, workshops, etc.)	> 5 conferences > 5 fairs > 2 workshops	- 6 conferences - 1 fair - 7 workshops - 1 brokerage event - 3 other types of events
Clustering activities	Clustering activities with other European related projects and the related European and National Technology Platforms, associations (ECTP, ECCREDI, FIEC).	> 2 cluster events participation > 1 cluster event organization/co-organization	- 1 cluster event participation - 3 cluster workshops organization
Thematic portals	Liaison and promotion of the Project on relevant thematic portals (BuildUp) and other relevant news and community portals.	> 5 press releases on thematic portals > 2 000 views	- 8 press releases on thematic portals - 3 252 views

4 Project identity and public image

Visual and graphic point of view allows an easier identification for the public as well as an improved visibility to obtain a brand for the EnDurCrete project during the dissemination activities, as shown in the following section.

4.1 Project logo

EnDurCrete logo was created by RINA-C already at the proposal stage in order to define a project identity, so clearly to identify any kind of internal or public document. EnDurCrete logo consists of grey cube representing concrete product, which is the core of the project. The green side of the cube illustrates the fact that the concrete developed under the EnDurCrete project takes into consideration environmental aspects and is expected to have improved LCA compared to traditional concrete. The second component of the logo consists of the name of the project in corresponding colours. Project logo can be used in the following cases:

- in all documents developed under the framework of the EnDurCrete project; in documents to be submitted to the EC (e.g. deliverables)
- in PowerPoint presentations to be used for communication and dissemination activities to be carried out by each participant under the framework of the project; in all promo material
- in EnDurCrete website, and in websites of the Participants with a link to the project website

Figure 4: EnDurCrete logo and its applications

Logo manual was developed in order to help partners correctly use the logo. EnDurCrete logo must be positioned in its own clear space away from design elements such as text and images. This will allow maximum stand out of the logo. The clear zone for each signature is calculated by using the letter “e”. Keeping always a clear space, EnDurCrete logo should be used at the same height than the rest of the logos.

Logo manual download: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/filedelivery.php?docId=59>

Figure 5: EnDurCrete logo clear zone and relation to other logos

The logo is composed of three colours: Green, Light grey, and Dark Grey. The palette is shown in the figure below.

Figure 6: EnDurCrete logo colour palette

As stated in the EnDurCrete Grant Agreement and article 27.3 Information on EU funding applications for protection of results (including patent applications) filed by or on behalf of a beneficiary must - unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible - include the following:

“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 760639”.

Figure 7: EU logo

5 Project promo material

FENIX designed promo material (brochure and roll up poster) in English at month M6 to support partners in dissemination events and raise awareness about the project. Additional dissemination material (project presentation) was created in month M7. This promo material will be updated minimum twice per project duration in order to provide readers the latest information and news about the project. More details about EnDurCrete dissemination material can be found in the deliverable D8.3 “Promo material design”.

Link to download EnDurCrete promo material: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material>

Figure 8: EnDurCrete brochure design

Figure 9: EnDurCrete roll up poster

6 Project website

The EnDurCrete website is considered in WP8 as one of the key elements for communication with public. The website is hosted by FENIX through the domain endurcrete.eu. The design was developed by FENIX at month M3 with the collaboration of the whole consortium. Website was designed considering display on different devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet. The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished (minimum 2 years). The website was designed to quickly address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- What is the project progress?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The website is split into two sections - private and public. The public section contains:

- general information about the project,
- partners' details,
- list of events and news,
- all public documents generated during the project,
- links to social network profiles,
- newsletter subscription,
- contact information,
- cluster projects,
- workshops registration,
- photo gallery.

The second part of the website is a private section that is available to FENIX (as an administrator) and to the project partners. The private section is accessed via log-in credentials. This restricted section is used for storage of:

- information about meetings,
- deliverables and management reports,
- administrative documents and forms,
- planned publications,
- work packages,
- templates and promo material,
- other documents.

Website cookies policy and google analytics were implemented (number of visitors, users, sessions, countries, languages, downloads, etc.). More information about the project website can be found in the deliverable D8.1 “Project website”. Statistics of promo material downloads are regularly tracked; the detailed numbers are listed in the following table. So far more than 4 000 public documents were downloaded up to month M24.

Table 2: Promo material and other downloads statistics

Promo material type	Downloads at M24
Logo, logo manual	609
Project presentation + updates	213
Brochure + updates	468
Roll-up poster + updates	405
First and second newsletter	170
Common newsletter AMANAC workshop	350
Flyer AMANAC workshop	103
Presentations from AMANAC workshop	71
Public deliverables	1 549
Videos	67
Articles in magazine	272
SUM	4 277

The starting page is called “Home” and it summarizes the basic information about the EnDurCrete project. The upper part of the screen shows a navigation panel, using a standard horizontal structure. At the top of the page, the project logo with the project acronym are placed, as the user scrolls the page down, shortened sections of the actual pages such as “About the Project”, latest “News & Events”, and “Partners” are listed. These parts of the home page are used as links to the actual pages, where the full content is displayed. The bottom of the home page includes EU logo, funding statement, Twitter feed online and subscribe button for the project Newsletter. Home page was recently updated with the project videos implementation into the design.

In the section “About the project” description of the concept, technology and demo sites are included. Newly added section is called “Cluster projects” and it is dedicated to the promotion of EnDurCrete sister projects (RESHEALIENCE, ECO-BINDER, DACOMAT, INNOVA CONCRETE, LORCENIS) in order to increase their visibility. The “Documents” page is split into subsections Promo material, Presentations, Newsletters, Publications, Papers, Reports and Other. Subsections can be added based on the project requirements at any time by the administrator (FENIX). The Documents page contains all material that is published and is thus publicly available (respecting copyright issues). Page “News & Events” presents a list of news and events where EnDurCrete project was presented or other activities related to the dissemination of the project results. The “Partners” section is shown as an interactive panel on the home page. When a user clicks on an individual partner's logo, a table with a short partner description and a hyperlink to their website appears. “Gallery” page collects all the photos from events where project was presented, GA meetings, etc. The last part of the public section contains contact information of the Project coordinator. It is intended for any inquiries by interested parties. Ad-hoc section “Workshop registration” was created specifically for the public workshops organized by the project.

The screenshot shows the EnDurCrete website home page. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Home, About the project, Cluster projects, Documents, News & Events, Gallery, and Partners. Below the navigation is the main header with the EnDurCrete logo and a tagline: "New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications".

The main content area is divided into several sections:

- About the Project:** A section describing the project's goal to develop a new cost-effective sustainable reinforced concrete. It includes a starting date of 1. 1. 2018 and a duration of 42 months. A "More about the project..." button is present.
- Project videos:** Two video thumbnails are shown. The first is titled "EnDurCrete Project - Sensor Video 2" and shows a network of sensors. The second is titled "EnDurCrete Concrete Samples" and shows workers in a lab setting. A caption below the second video reads: "Four panels (50x50x10 cm) and a block (50x10x10 cm) were cast to perform parametric analyses on the response of the self-sensing properties of concrete".
- News & Events:** A section with three items:
 - Load tests on concrete panels:** A video thumbnail with a YouTube icon.
 - New Endurcrete video:** A video thumbnail with a play button icon.
 - We are on INSTAGRAM:** A social media icon for Instagram.
- Social Media:** A section displaying a tweet from the @Endurcrete_eu account. The tweet text is: "2nd @Endurcrete_eu Project newsletter is out! Learn the latest news about the project, its status and recent events. We hope you will enjoy it! #endurcrete.eu/filedelivery.p... #H2020 #EnhancedConcrete #concrete #cement #eu @EU_H2020 @H2020Projects #panels #sensors #panels".
- Partners:** A row of logos for partner organizations: ems ADVANCED MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS, KVERNER, ZAG, and HEIDELBERGCEMENT Group.
- Footer:** A section containing the European Union logo, a disclaimer about funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, and a "Subscribe Newsletter" form with a text input field and a "Subscribe" button.

Figure 10: EnDurCrete website – home page

Figure 11: About the project section

Figure 12: Public documents section

Figure 13: News & Events section

Figure 14: Partners section

Figure 15: Contact section

Figure 16: Workshop registration page

The reserved area is accessed only by the project partners. Each partner is provided with a username and password in order to validate their access to the secure area. In this section the administrator (FENIX) can manage to update section News and Events, upload public and private documents, upload pictures to the Gallery and make changes of the website content. The project partners are enabled to upload and manage private documents.

Figure 17: Reserved Area section – Login

Figure 18: Reserved Area – Restricted files

In order to define process of website maintenance and update between FENIX and project partners, the following schema was defined.

Figure 19: Working with the website – schema

6.1 Website statistics

FENIX constantly monitors statistics regarding the number of the website visits, users, sessions as well as the demographics, geographic and language. Current statistics show a wide interest and public awareness regarding the project.

At month M24, project website has reached 14 545 views by 1 933 users. The biggest percentage of visitors comes from Spain (13,57%), followed by visitors from the United States (12,80%), Italy (10,72%), France (5,69%), and Germany (5,64%). Male visitors are represented by 54,15% and female by 45,85% in the age between 18-54.

Link to EnDurCrete project website: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/>

Figure 20: Website statistics – pageviews

Figure 21: Website statistics – locations and users

Figure 22: Website statistics – Age and gender

7 Project presentation

The project presentation in PowerPoint format was designed at month M7. The presentation describes the project concept, main objectives, project partners and demo sites. Furthermore, contact information and the statement of financial support to indicate that the foreground was generated with the assistance of financial support from the European Commission are given. The project presentation is a crucial part of the dissemination of the project, as it serves as a tool to inform the public about the basic characteristics of a newly developed product. The aim is to address a wide range of prospect consumers and ensure its memorability.

Link to download EnDurCrete project presentation:

<http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/presentation>

The figure displays a series of 12 slides from the EnDurCrete project presentation, arranged in a 3x4 grid. Each slide includes the endurcrete logo and the date 06/11/2019.

- Slide 1 (Title):** EnDurCrete project presentation. It features the endurcrete logo and text: "New Environmental friendly and Durable concrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications". It also mentions funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 760639.
- Slide 2 (Project Overview):** EnDurCrete Project. It states: "New Environmental friendly and Durable concrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore application". The main goal is to develop a new cost-effective sustainable reinforced concrete for long lasting and added value applications.
- Slide 3 (Partners):** Partners. It lists "16 partners from 12 countries" and shows a map of Europe with logos for various partners including NTNU, KVERNER, ZAG, HEIDELBERGCEMENT, VITO, RIFA, and others.
- Slide 4 (Project objective):** Project objective. The concept is based on the integration of novel low-linker cement including high-value industrial by-products, new nano and micro technologies and hybrid systems ensuring enhanced durability of sustainable concrete structures with high mechanical properties, self-healing and self-monitoring capacities. Key technologies include nano-enabled smart corrosion inhibitors, self-sensing carbon-based nanofillers, multifunctional coatings with self-healing properties, sensorised non-metallic reinforcement systems, and novel cement (CEM II/C and CEM VI).
- Slide 5 (Overall concept at a glance):** Overall concept at a glance. It lists novel technologies and tools: Novel CEM II/C and CEM VI cements, Novel low cost smart fillers, Advanced non-destructive continuous and testing tools and procedures, New multifunctional coatings, Concrete non-metallic multifunctional reinforcing systems, and Coupled experimental and computational approach for theoretical and experimental understanding of factors affecting durability. It also shows images of various concrete components and testing equipment.
- Slide 6 (Overall Approach):** Overall Approach. It outlines the approach: Test functionality of new concrete technologies under severe operating conditions (4 demo-sites), Develop experimental and numerical tools to understand factors affecting the durability and to capture the multiscale evolution of damage, and Develop models for service life prediction. The expected impact includes strengthening competitiveness of the European industry, positive LCA balance, at least 30% improved durability, and at least 30% lower cost.
- Slide 7 (Demosite):** Demosite. It states: "Demonstrators will be tested in working sites of tunnels, ports, and offshore structures, in order to prove the enhanced durability and decreased cost of the new concrete systems in such critical applications. Innovation aspects such standardization, life cycle assessments, health and safety and training activities will be addressed." It lists four demo sites: 1. Port of Gijón "El Musel" in Spain, 2. Mining tunnel facility in Leon, Spain, 3. Ship Yard in Norway, and 4. Rik Bridge in Croatia.
- Slide 8 (Contact Info):** Contact Info. It provides contact information for Dr. Arnaud Muller, HeidelbergCement, including his phone number and email address. It also provides the website www.endurcrete.eu and social media profiles for Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube.
- Slide 9 (Thank you):** Thank you for your attention. It features the endurcrete logo and logos of all project partners, including dms, KVERNER, ZAG, HEIDELBERGCEMENT Group, VITO, RIFA, GEONARDO, acciona, and others. It also mentions funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 760639.

Figure 23: Project presentation

8 Social media

In order to raise a public awareness about the EnDurCrete project, following social network profiles were created – LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram at the very beginning of the project – and their links were added to the project website and to all e-newsletters. FENIX, as the administrator of the profiles, manages the updates and posts, at least once a week.

Figure 24: EnDurCrete Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn (created M1)

Figure 25: EnDurCrete Instagram (created M18)

FENIX monitors the statistics of each social profile monthly. The detailed data showing the number of followers and impressions of each profile are shown in the following table.

Table 3: Social Media Statistics

Social Media Statistics	Followers/subscribers (M24)	Impressions/views (M24)
Facebook	54	1 960
Twitter	75	50 873
LinkedIn	76	6 723
Instagram	54	N/A
YouTube	7	255
Total	266	59 811

Links to EnDurCrete social network profiles:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Endurcrete-Project-985734441580566/>
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/Endurcrete_eu
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/11425986>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/endurcrete/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCCABicB3odCyTBgjmBD3xcQ>

9 e-Newsletter and press release

EnDurCrete e-Newsletters are released every six months. First e-Newsletter was designed by FENIX with technical contribution of project partners at month M13, second newsletter at month M22. Subscription is possible directly from the project website. EnDurCrete newsletters are promoted through social network profiles, project website, BuildUp portal, EU Agenda and project partners' channels. At M24 the both newsletters had together 170 downloads from the project website and 60 subscribers. Newsletter subscription follows General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regarding the protection of personal data.

Link to EnDurCrete newsletters download from the project website:

<http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/newsletters>

Figure 26: Newsletter subscription on the project website

Figure 27: First EnDurCrete newsletter (released M13)

Figure 28: Second EnDurCrete newsletter (released M22)

As part of the cluster activities, a common newsletter related to recent events co-organized by EnDurCrete project together with cluster projects (RESHEALIENCE, LORCENIS) was designed by FENIX and release at month M18. This newsletter was composed of a brief introduction of all three projects and a description of the main technologies that these projects cover together. From the two common workshops that projects co-organized (B-SMART within Made Expo, Milano, March 2019; PPCC, Madrid, March 2019), all speakers were introduced and links allowed to download their presentations publicly. Invitation to the planned common events was included as well (AMANAC workshop, Brussels, July 2019; LORCENIS conference, Ghent, July 2019). At month M24 this newsletter has reached 350 downloads from the project website. This newsletter was sent to 200 email addresses (cluster project's partners, events participants, newsletter subscribers, etc.).

The screenshot displays a multi-column newsletter layout. The top left features the 'endurcrete' logo and the date 'MAY 2019'. The main content is organized into several sections:

- INTRODUCTION:** Discusses the three H2020 projects (RESHEALIENCE, LORCENIS, B-SMART) and their goals in improving construction sustainability.
- TOPICS AND SPEAKERS:** A central column listing various topics such as 'THINK AND DESIGN THE DURABILITY OF CEMENT MATERIALS', 'MEASURE AND MONITOR DURABILITY', and 'DESIGN WITH DURABILITY: LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS', each with a 'READ MORE' link.
- PANEL ANALYSES OF PREDICTIVE ACTIONS:** A right-hand column detailing panel discussions on predictive actions, including health monitoring, self-healing, and latent corrective actions.
- FINAL ANALYSES AND CONCLUSIONS:** A section at the bottom right summarizing the findings and conclusions from the events.
- RECENT COMMON EVENTS:** A bottom-left section highlighting past events like 'B-SMART COMFORT, SAFETY, SUSTAINABILITY, INNOVATION' and 'PPCC2019'.
- UPCOMING EVENTS:** A bottom-right section for the 'NEXT PLANNED COMMON EVENT' (AMANAC WORKSHOP & LORCENIS CONFERENCE).

The newsletter uses a blue and white color scheme with red accents for key sections. It includes numerous images, logos of partner organizations, and links to external resources.

Figure 29: Common cluster newsletter (released M18)

EnDurCrete project is publishing press releases on various portals with topic of energy efficiency and sustainability, such as BuildUp portal, ECTP, EU Agenda, Research Gate, etc. EnDurCrete is also regularly publishing short posts on the project website, up to month M24 43 short news were posted.

The screenshot shows a document titled "endurcrete" with the following content:

endurcrete

EnDurCrete: New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications

The EnDurCrete project is a newly launched research project supported by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme for Research and Innovation (Call H2020-NMBP-2017-two-stage, Project No. 760639) which started in January 2018 with a duration of 42 months. The project consortium is led by HeidelbergCement and it consists of sixteen partners from twelve European countries (Germany, Italy, France, Spain, Norway, Switzerland, Slovenia, Belgium, Czech Republic, Hungary, Greece and Croatia). Six out of 16 partners are SME's. Each partner has specific and high-value knowledge in all the scientific and technological branches that are necessary to meet the project goals.

Project objective

The main goal of the EnDurCrete Project is to develop a new cost-effective sustainable reinforced concrete for long lasting and added value applications. The concept is based on the integration of novel low-clinker cement including high-value industrial by-products, new nano and micro technologies and hybrid systems ensuring enhanced durability of sustainable concrete structures with high mechanical properties, self-healing and self-monitoring capacities. The key EnDurCrete technologies are: nano-enabled smart corrosion inhibitors, self-sensing carbon-based nanofillers, multifunctional coatings with self-healing properties and sensorised non-metallic reinforcement systems. Innovative design concepts will be developed for smart installation, disassembly and re-use of the new green pre-cast and cast in place elements aiming at enabling easy recycling and re-using approaches.

Demonstrations

The functionality of the developed concrete structures will be proved under severe operating conditions supported by experimental and numerical tools to better understand factors affecting durability and capture the multiscale evolution of damage as well as to enable service life prediction. Demonstrators will be tested in working sites of tunnels, ports and offshore structures, in order to prove the enhanced durability and decreased cost of the new concrete systems in such critical applications. Four demonstrations will be located in Spain, Norway, and Croatia.

EnDurCrete consortium met during the Kick-off meeting on 16th January 2018 in Brussels, Belgium. The project partners introduced themselves and discussed the planned activities for the next six-month period within the work packages. It was a great opportunity for partners to meet each other face-to-face and to establish successful cooperation.

Project partners

EnDurCrete is coordinated by HeidelbergCement and will be run in cooperation with 15 European partners: **ADVANCED MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS, KVAERNER, ZAG, UNIVERSITA TECHNICA DELLE MARCHE, VITO, INFRA PLAN KONZALTING, RINA, SIKA, NORWEGIAN UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, NUOVA TESI SYSTEM, IBOX, GEONARDO, FENIX TNT, ACCIONA, and CEA.**

Notes for editors:

"The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 760639"

Press and media enquiries can be directed to:

Coordinator: Dr. Arnaud Muller, arnaud.muller@htc-gmbh.com, +49 6221 4811 3676
Dissemination & Exploitation manager: petra.colantonio@fenixtnt.cz, +420 732 822 538

Figure 30: EnDurCrete first press release (with instructions for partners spreading)

BUILD UP The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings

Home News & Events Practices Learn Explore Topics Skills **Practices** SEARCH

Build Up Home / Practices

View published Translate

Revision state: Published
Most recent revision: Yes

EnDurCrete: New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications

25 June 2018 / 0 Undefined

Share this Post: [f](#) [t](#) [s](#) [in](#) [x](#)

Information about this post

Type of News News from European projects

Themes Energy efficiency technologies and materials, Environmental issues related to buildings, General

Target Group Local/regional/national authorities and facilitators, Building professionals

Website URL(s) <http://www.endurcrete.eu/>

Author(s) (organisation) FENIX TNT s.r.o.

Submitted by: Petra Colantonio (FENIX TNT s.r.o.)

Source languages English

Tag Cloud

H2020 - Horizon 2020

endurcrete

The EnDurCrete project is a newly launched research project supported by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme for Research and Innovation (Call H2020-NMMP-2017 two-stage, Project No. 760629) which started in January 2018 with a duration of 42 months. The project consortium is led by HeidelbergCement and it consists of sixteen partners from twelve European countries (Germany, Italy, France, Spain, Norway, Switzerland, Slovenia, Belgium, Czech Republic, Hungary, Greece and Croatia). Six out of 16 partners are SMEs. Each partner has specific and high-value knowledge in all the scientific and technological branches that are necessary to meet the project goals.

Project objective

The main goal of the EnDurCrete Project is to develop a new cost-effective sustainable reinforced concrete for long lasting and added value applications. The concept is based on the integration of novel low-clinker cement including high-value industrial by-products, new nano and micro technologies and hybrid systems ensuring enhanced durability of sustainable concrete structures with high mechanical properties, self-healing and self-monitoring capacities. The key EnDurCrete technologies are: nano-enabled smart corrosion inhibitors, self-sensing carbon-based nanofillers, multifunctional coatings with self-healing properties and sensorised non-metallic reinforcement systems. Innovative design concepts will be developed for smart installation, disassembly and re-use of the new green pre-cast and cast in place elements aiming at enabling easy recycling and re-using approaches.

Demonstrations

The functionality of the developed concrete structures will be proved under severe operating conditions supported by experimental and numerical tools to better understand factors affecting durability and capture the multiscale evolution of damage as well as to enable service life prediction. Demonstrators will be tested in working sites of tunnels, ports and offshore structures, in order to prove the enhanced durability and decreased cost of the new concrete systems in such critical applications. Four demonstrations will be located in Spain, Norway, and Croatia.

EnDurCrete consortium met during the Kick-off meeting on 16th January 2018 in Brussels, Belgium. The project partners introduced themselves and discussed the planned activities for the next six-month period within the work packages. It was a great opportunity for partners to meet each other face-to-face and to establish successful cooperation.

Project partners

EnDurCrete is coordinated by HEIDELBERG CEMENT and will be run in cooperation with 15 European partners: ADVANCED MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS, WÄRMENER, ZAG, UNIVERSITA' TECNICA DELLE MARCHE, VITO, INFRA PLAN KONZALTING, RINA, SIKI, NORWEGIAN UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, NUOVA TEST SYSTEM, IBOV, GEONARDO, FENIX TNT, ACCIONS, and CEA.

The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 760629.

Source: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/>

News Life: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/>

 Sustainable durable cement

 Self-healing and self-monitoring fibres and coatings

 Sensorised non-metallic reinforcing system

 Durability modelling, testing, monitoring and standardisation

BUILD UP The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings

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View published Translate

Revision state: Published
Most recent revision: Yes

EnDurCrete project: new video

11 September 2018 / 9 Other european countries Pan European EU Institutions International Organizations

Share this Post: [f](#) [t](#) [s](#) [in](#) [x](#)

Information about this post

Type of News News from European projects

Themes Energy efficiency technologies and materials, Environmental issues related to buildings

Target Group Local/regional/national authorities and facilitators, Building professionals, Building occupants

Author(s) (organisation) Petra Colantonio

Submitted by: Petra Colantonio (FENIX TNT s.r.o.)

Source languages English

Tag Cloud

H2020 - Horizon 2020

endurcrete

New video
Concrete samples

The EnDurCrete project is a newly launched research project supported by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme for Research and Innovation (Call H2020-NMMP-2017 two-stage, Project No. 760629) which started in January 2018 with a duration of 42 months. The project consortium is led by HeidelbergCement and it consists of sixteen partners from twelve European countries (Germany, Italy, France, Spain, Norway, Switzerland, Slovenia, Belgium, Czech Republic, Hungary, Greece and Croatia). Six out of 16 partners are SMEs. Each partner has specific and high-value knowledge in all the scientific and technological branches that are necessary to meet the project goals.

During the last meeting at the Nuova Test System facilities, four samples of concrete were cast to perform parametric analyses of the self-sensing properties of concrete.

Take a look [HERE](#)

And don't forget to follow our YouTube channel!

Source: 433 reads

Permalink: <https://www.buildup.eu/en/node/58113>

Figure 31: EnDurCrete press releases on BuildUp

Number of views on BuildUp at M24:

- General EnDurCrete project introduction – 2 130m views
- EnDurCrete project panel samples – 433 views

Figure 32: EnDurCrete press releases on EU Agenda

Number of views on EU Agenda:

- EnDurCrete graphical video – redirected to YouTube channel
- EnDurCrete concrete panels video – redirected to YouTube channel
- EnDurCrete load tests on concrete panels – redirected to YouTube channel
- EnDurCrete project general introduction – 672 views

Figure 33: EnDurCrete press releases on ECTP

The screenshot shows the Research Gate project page for "ENDURCRETE PROJECT" by Petra Colantonio. The page features a navigation bar with "Home", "Questions", and "Jobs" links, and a search bar. The project overview includes statistics: 5 updates, 0 recommendations, 0 followers, and 6 reads. The "Project log" section is active, displaying five updates:

- Load tests on concrete panels** (24s ago): A text-based update describing load tests on concrete panels for the Horizon 2020 project, mentioning sensors and data analysis.
- Project video** (Jun 21): A graphical video update with a link to "EnDurCrete_Promo video_Final_v2.mp4" (13.46 MB) and 5 reads.
- ENDURETE first newsletter** (Jun 21): A text-based update about a 6-month e-newsletter, with a link to "EnDurCrete_1st newsletter_January 2019.pdf" (3.36 MB) and 5 reads.
- ENDURETE brochure with general info about the project** (Jun 21): A text-based update with a link to "EnDurCrete_Brochure_Sep 2018_print.pdf" (3.15 MB) and 4 reads.
- Project goal** (Jun 21): A text-based update stating the project's goal: "New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications." It details the goal of developing a new cost-effective sustainable reinforced concrete.

Figure 34: EnDurCrete press releases on Research Gate

Number of views on Research Gate:

- EnDurCrete project general introduction – 3 views
- EnDurCrete brochure – 4 views
- EnDurCrete first newsletter – 5 views
- EnDurCrete graphical video – 5 views

10 Videos

One of the key methods for the effective product dissemination is the creation and publication of videos. FENIX with in-house video production leads the videos creation for EnDurCrete project and project YouTube channel was created as well.

(<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCcABicB3odCyTBgjmBD3xcQ>). So far, a graphical video and short videos from the Nuova Tesi laboratory were released.

The promo video is planned to be designed towards the end of the project when technology is fully developed and tested at demo sites. It will include interviews, photos, filming, graphics, music and voice over. The video presentation is meant to follow the successive introduction to the strategies regarding the “WWW campaigns”: social media, workshops, web advertising in general.

Figure 35: YouTube channel for EnDurCrete project

First project graphical video was created by FENIX and released in month M16. So far (M24), the video has 178 views. The video focuses on the general introduction of the project and its main concept, objectives, expected impact and demo-site details.

Figure 36: EnDurCrete graphical video

Second video, created by Nuova Tesi and released at month M20, is dedicated to sensorized concrete panels production in Nuova Tesi laboratory, including mechanical testing and textile reinforcement. So far (month M24), the video has 180 views.

Figure 37: EnDurCrete concrete panels video

Third video, created by Nuova Tesi and released at month M21, is dedicated also to concrete panels production in Nuova Tesi laboratory, where the team from the Università Politecnica delle Marche came to install sensors for measuring the electrical impedance of concrete. Four panels (50x50x10

cm) and a block (50x10x10 cm) were cast to perform the parametric analysis on the response of the self-sensing properties of concrete. So far (month M24), the video has 137 views.

Figure 38: EnDurCrete concrete samples video

Fourth video, created by Nuova Tesi and release at month M22, is dedicated to load tests on concrete panels in Nuova Tesi laboratory. At first the stress test was carried out on the panel with traditional reinforcement, then on the panel reinforced with synthetic net. So far (month M24), the video has 118 views.

Figure 39: EnDurCrete load tests on concrete panels video

11 Publications

As stated in Article 29.2 each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication—via the repository—at the latest:

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable;
- a persistent identifier.

Partners are publishing articles about the EnDurCrete project in popularized and technical magazines. Project partners will publish the results also in the scientific literature and dedicated journals. EnDurCrete publications will be made accessible through either the Green Open Access or Gold Access model in accordance with H2020 guidelines on Open Access. Zenodo profile has been created to store project publications and research data.

11.1 Green open access

The green open access is also called self-archiving and means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived by the researcher in an online repository (ae.g. Zenodo, Openaire, etc.) before, after or alongside its publication. Access to this article is often delayed (embargo period). Publishers recoup their investment by selling subscriptions and charging pay-per-download/view fees during this period during an exclusivity period. This model is promoted alongside the “Gold” route by the open access community of researchers and librarians and is often preferred.

11.2 Gold open access

This type of open access is sometimes called open access publishing, or author pays publishing and means that a publication is immediately provided in open access mode by the scientific publisher. Associate costs are shifted from readers to the university or research institute to which the researcher is affiliated, or to the funding agency supporting the research. This model is usually the one promoted by the community of well-established scientific publishers in the business.

Figure 40: EnDurCrete profile on Zenodo

The list of scientific and popularized publications performed for the EnDurCrete project is shown in the table below. Project has managed 1 publication in journal, 2 bachelor thesis, 1 chapter in book, 5 magazine publications and 1 project work.

Figure 41: Graph of publications performed for EnDurCrete project and partner's involvement

Table 1: List of publications

Publication title	Link	Publication type	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Periodical name/ Publisher	Number, Date	Place	Relevant pages	Public & private participation	Peer /review	Open access	Partner /s	Status
Concrete eco friendly	https://view.publitas.com/platinum-online/2018-luglio_ita/page/1 http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/publications/polarized-publications	Publication in magazine	10.5281/zenodo.3234668	ISSN 2038-2596	Marco Nucci, Francesco Talin, Gabriella Breda	Platinum magazine, publisher New Business Media	July 2018	Italy	96	NO	YES	YES	NUOVA TESI	Performed
Rilevazione di difettosità superficiali nel calcestruzzo mediante sistemi di visione (Detection of surface defects in concrete by machine vision systems)	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Giacomo Salucci Advisor: Gian Marco Revel Co-advisor: Paolo Chiariotti	N.A.	30/10/2018	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Performed
Analisi non distruttiva di componenti in cemento tramite ultrasuoni (Non-destructive analysis of cement components by means of ultrasound technique)	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Francesco Senesi Advisor: Gian Marco Revel Co-advisor: Giuseppe Pandarese	N.A.	19/12/2018	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Performed

Influenza del tempo di stagionatura e dell'umidità relativa sulle proprietà elettriche e meccaniche di malte con capacità self-sensing contenenti alti dosaggi di filler (Influence of curing time and relative humidity on the electrical and mechanical properties of self-sensing mortars containing high dosages of filler)	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Francesco Canali Advisor: Francesca Tittarelli Co-advisors: Alessandra Mobili, Tiziano Bellezze	N.A.	22/02/2019	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Planned
Influenza del tempo di stagionatura e dell'umidità relativa sulle proprietà elettriche e meccaniche di malte con capacità self-sensing contenenti bassi dosaggi di filler (In English: Influence of curing time and relative humidity on the electrical and mechanical properties of self-sensing mortars containing low dosages of filler)	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Alessia Bistosini Advisor: Francesca Tittarelli Co-advisors: Alessandra Mobili, Tiziano Bellezze	N.A.	22/02/2019	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Planned
Caratterizzazione di campioni in cemento tramite tecnica ultrasonora (In English: Characterization of	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Antonio Pio Colosanto Advisor: Gian Marco Revel Co-advisor:	N.A.	25/07/2019	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Planned

cement specimens by means of ultrasound technique)					Giuseppe Pandarese									
Durable, low-impact concrete	https://www.cemnet.com/sample/magazine/icr-september-2018-sample/index.html http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/publications/polarized-publications	Publication in magazine	10.5281/zenodo.3234599	ISSN 0959-6038	PetraColantonio, FENIX TNTsr o, Czech Republic, and P Blaum, PDurdzinska and AMuller, Heidelberg Cement AG, Germany	International Cement Review (ICR), publisher Tradeship Publications Ltd.	Sep 2018	United Kingdom	52	NO	NO	YES	FEN/ HC	Performed
Development of composite cements characterized by low environmental footprint	N.A.	Article in journal	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.050	N.A.	Gerd Bolte, Maciej Zajac, Jan Skocek, Mohsen Ben Haha	Journal of Cleaner Production, publisher Elsevier BV	Volume 226, July 2019	Netherlands	503-514	NO	YES	NO	HC	Performed
Production optimization of composite cements with low environmental footprint	https://www.zkg.de/en/artikel/zkg_20th_International_Conference_on_Building_Materials_ibausil_2994094.html	Chapters in book	-	978-3-00-059950-7	Gerd Bolte, Maciej Zajac, Mohsen Ben Haha	20. International Conference on Building Materials "ibausil", Weimar, publisher Finger-Institut für Baustoffkunde	Sep 2018	Weimar, Germany	641-650	NO	NO	No	HC	Performed

The EnDurCrete project	http://www.europeanenergyinnovation.eu/OnlinePublication/Summer2019/mobile/index.html#p=34	Publication in magazine	N/A	2219-9446	Martina Bakešová	European Energy Innovation magazine, publisher Prologue Media Ltd.	July 2019	United Kingdom	35	NO	NO	YES	FEN	Performed
Ny sement for bedre miljø	www.bygg.no	Publication in magazine	No DOI available	0332-7086	Alisa Machner, Marie Helene Bjørndal, Klaartje De Weerd	Byggeindustrien	October 2019	Norway	1	NO	NO	Green	NTNU	Performed
Valorizzazione di sottoprodotti industriali biobased per calcestruzzi self-sensing (In English: Valorization of biobased industrial byproducts for self-sensing concrete)	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Alessio Migliori Advisor: Francesca Tittarelli Co-advisor: Alessandra Mobili	N.A.	December 2019	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Planned
Sviluppo di un Sistema di misura per il monitoraggio dello stato di salute nel tempo di nuove composizioni di calcestruzzo (In English: Development of a measurement system for the monitoring over time of the health status of different concrete compositions)	N.A.	Bachelor Thesis	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Andrea Evangelista Advisor: Gian Marco Revel Co-advisors: Gloria Cosoli, Giuseppe Pandarese	N.A.	February 2020	Italy	N.A.	NO	N.A.	YES	UNIVPM	Planned

Carbonation resistance of concrete and mortar containing novel low clinker cement	N.A.	Project work	N.A.	N.A.	Student: Marie Helene Bjørndal Advisor: Klaartje De Weerd Co-advisor: Alisa Machner	N.A.	30 September 2019	Trondheim, Norway	N.A.	NO	N.A.	Currently not	NTNU	Performed
Ny sement for bedre miljø	www.bygg.no	Publication in magazine	No DOI available	0332-7086	Alisa Machner, Marie Helene Bjørndal, Klaartje De Weerd	Byggeindustrien	October 2019	Norway	1	NO	NO	Green	NTNU	Performed

12 Training activities

Within the framework of training activities (planned from the month M24 till the end of the project), the technical sheets, instructions and tools relevant for the production, design, application and installation developed during the Project will be created and will be distributed among a wide community of professionals during the training activities. These activities will include videos, webinars and courses to support the training of individuals. In addition, an e-Learning platform will be developed and launched by GEO with the aim of allowing the interested users to easily access the training material and follow its modules at their convenience. I-BOX will provide support to training activities and technical content related to corrosion inhibitors and concrete in general, CEA will participate to the technical contents related to safety, AMSolution regarding coating application, and RINA-C, ACCIONA, KVAERNER regarding installation and monitoring activities.

13 Events organization and presentation

The Project will be concluded by a public workshop (attended by representatives of various industries and cities, officials, and other stakeholders) organized near one of the demo-sites. Regarding networking, special care is taken to participate to activities of ECCM (RINA-C and CEA), possibly contributing with inputs related to EnDurCrete modelling and simulation activities. To address the scientific and research community, policymakers and public authorities, the following conferences are in the focus of the consortium: ECTP Conference, Sustainable Places, Nordic Concrete Research Symposium, World of Concrete Europe etc. The EnDurCrete project is also presented during fairs and exhibitions focused on building materials, building innovations, technical solutions, concrete products, energy efficiency, etc. to raise awareness about the project among the industry, manufacturers, wide public.

13.1 Events organization with other projects

EnDurCrete project organized various public workshops mainly with two cluster projects (LORCENIS, ReSHEALience) in order to increase the dissemination impact, share knowledge and audience. The detailed description of the workshops performed together is listed below. The three H2020 projects are Research and Innovation Actions (RIA) that pertain to the field of nanotechnologies, being all of them related with cementitious composites. They share their vision of increasing the performance of the concrete and use them to multiply the structure durability and its control. The main construction sectors covered by the technologies developed to enhance durability in aggressive environments and sustainability: LORCENIS, started in 2016, is focused in energy infrastructures in severe operational environments (deep sea, freeze-thaw, mechanical, fatigue, high temperature, chemical attack...), while ReSHEALience complements, it being centred in two of the most common Aggressive Exposure Environments (chemical attack, XA and marine, XS). Both projects integrate nano-additives with new functionalities in high performance concretes, while

EnDurCrete integrates nano additives in low-carbon concretes, also oriented to more common construction spectrum of applications. The three strategies can be combined and even synergic and covered a TRL range between 5 to 7 of technologies. This will be proven in the different prototypes which will include, among others the testing of nanoparticles, advanced concretes and durability-design approaches can provide already at medium-term. Together, the prototypes will cover the specific knowledge of more than 45 partners, proving that the benefits of these developments can go far beyond the construction sector.

Figure 42: EnDurCrete, ReSHEAlience and Lorcenis project’s consortium

13.1.1 AMANAC workshop “Branding innovations beyond the technical Life Cycle Assessment and the trade-offs of sustainable growth”

With the environmental impacts of materials and processes gaining more attention, the desire and attempt to quantify these through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analyses in recent years has resulted in several international certifications and legislation strategies, aiming to inform decision-making. Despite Life Cycle Thinking being already widely accepted as a guiding principle for designing the EU product policy framework, the practical implementation of Life Cycle based decision-making has been quite limited, mainly because the needs of different end-users and stakeholders have not been properly acknowledged and/or effectively communicated. Therefore, this workshop (organised by AMANAC cluster partners for “Advanced Materials and Nanotechnology in Construction”) aimed to address the challenges and opportunities of Life Cycle based decision-making by offering different stakeholders a thorough review of various LCA technical and communication barriers, considering social and economic perspectives to facilitate a thorough and holistic sustainable approach.

The workshop was organized within the INDTECH 2018 (Innovative Industries for Smart Growth, Vienna, 29th – 31st October 2018), an event of the Austrian Presidency of the Council of the European Union. The INDTECH combined keynote presentations, talks, a matchmaking event and exhibitions. It provided an excellent opportunity to meet experts from industry, academia and policy to exchange information and to strengthen collaboration. INDTECH2018 anticipated 1000 participants from more than 30 countries in Europe and across the globe.

Figure 43: INDTECH2018 promo brochure

AMANAC workshop “Branding innovations beyond the technical Life Cycle Assessment and the trade-offs of sustainable growth” was organized on 29th October 2019 in Vienna, Austria and EnDurCrete project was represented by partners from Geonardo, Heidelberg cement and FENIX TNT.

Figure 44: Flyer for the AMANAC workshop “Branding innovations beyond the technical Life Cycle Assessment and the trade-offs of sustainable growth”

The workshop was a success, including fruitful discussions among the participants on various topics such as the importance of the LCA for Industrial Technologies, circular economy in construction, the priorities of the construction sector on materials and sustainability, social performance of buildings, problems concerning LCA in early product development phases, the needs for harmonised LCA standards for construction products in Europe, applications of

LCA for improving the branding of innovation and exploitation of new products. About 50 people from cluster projects including scientific community (university representatives, research organizations), engineering and industry companies, Project Officers from European Commission have participated in the workshop.

13.1.2 Common workshop “The concrete construction industry facing durability challenges: the Italian contribution in synergy with the European vision of the Horizon 2020 projects ReSHEALience and Endurcrete”

EnDurCrete and ReSHEALience project with the sponsorship of ACI Italy chapter organized within the B-SMART! a common workshop “The concrete construction industry facing durability challenges: the Italian contribution in synergy with the European vision of the Horizon 2020 projects ReSHEALience and Endurcrete”. The workshop was organized during the MADE Expo event on 14th March 2019 in Milan, Italy.

MADE Expo is Italy’s most important trade show for the Building & Construction industry and also one of Europe’s most significant events dedicated to the Architecture and the Construction sectors. Over 90,000 visitors, 900 exhibitors, 250 events and conferences with more than 14,000 participants. B-SMART! Comfort, Safety, Sustainability, Innovation was packed programme of conferences, workshops and labs on the fundamental issues of the construction world in a professional, engaging and interactive way. Conferences, prototypes and interactive labs provided valuable technical, scientific and regulatory insights into solutions, materials and technologies for the design, the renovation and the construction of comfortable, safe and sustainable buildings. Workshop was visited about 100 participants.

The common workshop was intended for all operators in the construction sector, with particular reference to concrete, from material and component producers to construction companies, building and infrastructure managers, and technical and administrative decision makers. The speakers, chosen from among the participants in the research groups involved, provided an updated overview of the most current issues concerning the durability of reinforced concrete structures and infrastructures and the most up-to-date solutions and methodologies to address them at the various technical-operational-decision levels. EnDurCrete project was represented by partners Università Politecnica delle Marche, Heidelberg cement, Nuova Tesi and RINA Consulting. A common newsletter (Figure 29: Common cluster newsletter) after the event was designed by FENIX and released at month M18 in order to promote all three projects, events organized and planned together, and to allow introduction of speakers and their presentations.

Common newsletter download: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/filedelivery.php?docid=254>

EnDurCrete presentations download: <http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/clustering-activities/made-expo-milano>

Figure 45: Photo report from B-SMART common workshop

Topics and speakers:

- “Think” and “design” the durability of cement materials: going beyond the current service life objectives
 - “Concept and design” of durability of cement-based materials: Going beyond the current service life targets; Liberato Ferrara - Politecnico di Milano, Italy - ReSHEALience project coordinator
 - Measure and “monitor” durability
 - Non-destructive techniques to measure and monitor the durability of concrete; Gian Marco Revel - Università Politecnica delle Marche, Italy – EnDurCrete project
 - Predictive monitoring systems for rebar corrosion assessment in aggressive environments; Maria Cruz Alonso, CSIC, Spain, ReSHEALience/Lorcenis projects
 - Novel carbon-based additions for self-sensing concretes; Francesca Tittarelli - Università Politecnica delle Marche, Italy – EnDurCrete project
 - Design with durability: life cycle analysis
 - Design with the durability: life-cycle analysis; M. Chiara Caruso - Consorzio Stress, Italy - ReSHEALience project
 - “Build durability”: The experience and the point of view of the “end-users” and stakeholders
 - Reduction of costs through extreme durability concretes: two successful stories; Esteban Camacho - Research and Development Concretes, Spain - ReSHEALience project
 - Application of high durability concrete (UHDC) in the industry; Francesco Animato - Enel Green Power, Italy - ReSHEALience project
 - Development of concrete panels reinforced with technical sensorized fabric; Paolo Corvaglia - Rina Consulting / Tesi System, Italy - EnDurCrete project

The workshop was quite a success, more than 65 people participated. All three projects had a chance to introduce their results, discuss lessons learned and upcoming challenges with the external audience.

13.1.3 Workshop within PPCC2019

In order to ensure durable performance for concrete structures, the current solutions are composed of complex and expensive maintenance programs. Non-active maintenance actions are the come forth new strategies for durability and extension of service life of concrete structures. The challenge is based on the integration of self-response properties into the concrete through the implementation of actions showing predictive, preventive or corrective capabilities. With this objective, technologies based on sustainability and durability have achieved rapid advances in concrete technology. Self-functional additives with self-curing, self-protection, self-healing and self-sensing functionalities have been developed, implemented in concretes and evaluated their performance in severe environments.

These functionalities have been discussed in the frame of the International Networking event under the name of Predictive- Preventive-Corrective Constructions (PPCC19) held in Madrid 19th March 2019. However, the practical application of this new technology needs for appropriate diffusion channels and dissemination forums where the latest advances are compared at the level of research and application expectances. The focus of the International Workshop was to provide a framework for the exchange of knowledge on the latest advances in research, on site applications and market needs in the field of construction.

This open discussion forum brought together more than 100 people from nine EU countries represented from construction industry, Ministries and academia. The aim of this international event was the analyses of expectances for implementation of emerging concrete technologies and additives based on “self-response capacity” and dissemination of project’s results.

Main topics evolved around sustainability, standardization, market assessment for durability and service-life of offshore concrete structures, health monitoring of structures, new materials for self-diagnosis in construction, crack self-healing technologies and challenges, actual needs and future expectances from new NON-active Maintenance.

EnDurCrete project was presented within the speech of J. Vera (ACCIONA Construction from Spain) during the session called Panel analyses of latent corrective actions.

Figure 46: Photo report from workshop within the PPCC2019

13.1.4 AMANAC workshop “What kind of built environment for future generations?”

Fostering research and innovation within construction materials can bring high impact for the European economy and for reaching a sustainable built environment. It offers new opportunities for the construction products and processes to strengthen the fight against pollution and to avoid dangerous effects on climate and/or human health. Another AMANAC workshop “What kind of built environment for future generations” was co-organized by the three AMANAC cluster projects EnDurCrete, ReSHEALience, DACOMAT on 3rd July 2019 in Brussels, Belgium providing on how the three projects focus on developing long-lasting and cost-effective construction materials and how they are contributing to the above-mentioned aims. The main aim was to show which are the challenges and the opportunities of these innovative and fit-for-the-purpose cement based and organic composites for the construction sector. This was done by addressing the point of view of the different actors involved in developing and managing a sustainable built environment.

The main topics discussed were:

- Advanced materials for long lasting built environment
 - Future cities: the impact of infrastructures on local communities
 - What is the contribution of ReSHEALience and EnDurCrete in the field of cement-based composites?
 - What is the contribution of DACOMAT in the field of organic composites?
- What are the challenges and needs for the actors in the construction industry?
 - The perspectives of cement and concrete producers
 - The perspective of a chemical company
 - The perspective of a construction company
 - The perspectives of a precast company
 - The perspectives of an engineering firm
 - The perspectives of actors in 3Dprinting initiatives
 - The perspectives of industry-oriented university research
- Making the professionals and the general public aware of the solutions for durable built environment
 - Educating to a longer lasting built environment: the perspective of universities
 - Designing for longer lasting built environment: a Life Cycle Analysis perspective
 - Bringing the solutions to the general public and the market: perspective by certification and standardization bodies
 - Implementing new materials and solutions- Perspective of architects
 - Exploiting new materials and solutions – Perspective of final end-users
 - Reaching the general public: the EnDurCrete & ReSHEALience strategies

The event was concluded by the interactive session on the topic “Developing solutions that last 100 years”.

FENIX has designed a promo flyer with the workshop agenda as shown on the picture below.

Figure 49: AMANAC workshop “What kind of built environment for future generations?” promotion through AMANAC website

Figure 50: AMANAC workshop “What kind of built environment for future generations?” promotion through ECTP portal

The workshop was attended by more than 70 people of different focus such industry, academic, research, engineers, architects, project representatives, Project Officers, etc.

Figure 51: Photo report from AMANAC workshop “What kind of built environment for future generations?”

13.2 Events participation

Over the last 24 months EnDurCrete project was presented during various types of events by project partners, detailed description of every event can be found in the following section below.

As a summary project was presented on 6 conferences, 1 fairs and exhibitions, 1 brokerage event, 7 workshops, 3 other events.

Figure 52: Graph of dissemination events for EnDurCrete project

Figure 53: Graph of EnDurCrete partners' activity in dissemination events

Event title	Start Up Olé 2018
Website	www.startupole.eu/2018/i-box-create http://startupeuroclub.eu/event/startup-ole-2018/
Location	Salamanca, Spain
Date	17-19 April 2018
Type of event	Fair
Responsible partner	i-BOXC
Event description	Event with the continuous support of Startup Europe (EC) showcasing startups and providing them with the right connections. It also provides a forum where startups can share experiences and develop synergies so that they can grow together. Start Ups selected from those with the Seal of Excellence from UE. EnDurCrete project participated as Start-Up.
Partner contribution	Brochure with information on the Nanocorrosion Inhibitors and the information of EndurCrete project.
Type of audience	Start Up community (Accelerators, Investors, Public Administrations, Policymakers, Universities, Talent)
Statistics	Over 850 start-ups, more then 2000 attendees.
Attachments	<div data-bbox="579 929 1324 1341" data-label="Image"> </div> <div data-bbox="579 1373 1324 1872" data-label="Image"> </div>

Event title	UK - Spain bilateral event for Nanotechnologies & Advanced Materials
Website	https://bilateral-event-for-nano-and-advanced-materials.b2match.io/
Location	Cambridge, United Kingdom
Date	15-16 May 2018
Type of event	Brokerage event
Responsible partner	ACCIONA
Event description	The main aim of the event was to foster cooperative partnerships in order to build prospective collaborative R&D project consortia for EU and nationally funded programmes such as Horizon 2020. The event also provided a platform for commercial and technological B2B partnerships as well as for R&D collaborations.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	SMEs, larger companies, technology centres and research organisation
Statistics	80 delegates (40 UK + 40 Spain)
Attachments	<p>The agenda for Wednesday 15 May 2018 includes the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 08:55 – 15:30: Agenda 15th May: Panel workshops at Jesus College - provisional timings below to be confirmed 09:00 – 09:05: Agenda 15th May: Welcome and Introduction – Chair – UK Government representative 09:05 – 09:30: Agenda 15th May: Inaugural Speech - Rt Hon Sam Gyimah, Minister for Universities, Science, Research and Innovation, Govt of UK 09:30 – 09:30: Agenda 15th May: "From Advanced Materials research to Real Products" - Professor Sir Colin Humphreys, University of Cambridge 09:30 – 09:50: Agenda 15th May: "Advanced Materials and Nanotechnologies in Construction Industry" - Mr Jose Cuabito, ACCIONA CONSTRUCTION SA 09:50 – 10:10: Agenda 15th May: Coffee Break 10:10 – 10:30: Agenda 15th May: "Accelerating Innovations to the Market" - the role of Incubators and Government Policy" - Dr Heng Hon Kuok, Comtech Management Pte Ltd 10:30 – 10:50: Agenda 15th May: "Pilot Production Clustering in Europe" - Dr Bojan Bokovic, Cambridge Nanomaterials Technology Ltd 10:50 – 12:00: Agenda 15th May: Panel Discussion on Advanced Materials and Nanotechnologies Development Strategy (European, International, Bi-national, National, Regional) 12:00 – 13:00: Agenda 15th May: Lunch 13:00 – 14:00: Agenda 15th May: Panel Discussion on Advanced Materials and Nanotechnologies Industrial Strategy (Multinationals, LE and SMEs) 14:00 – 15:05: Agenda 15th May: Panel Discussion on Advanced Materials and Nanotechnologies Research Infrastructure Development Strategy (RTOs, Universities, Innovation Hubs) 15:05 – 15:15: Agenda 15th May: Tea/Coffee Break

Event title	China Academy of Building Research
Website	N/A
Location	Brno, Czech Republic
Date	26 June 2018
Type of event	Discussion
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	EnDurCrete project was introduced to the representatives of the China Academy of Building Research (CABR) who visited the FENIX TNT premises. CABR is the largest comprehensive R&D institution in the building sector in China.
Partner contribution	Project introduction within the FENIX company presentation as one of the H2020 project in portfolio, dissemination of brochures.
Type of audience	Meeting with 4 representatives of the China Academy of Building Research
Statistics	4 representatives of the China Academy of Building Research
Attachments	

Event title	ECOBINDER workshop
Website	http://ecobinder-project.eu/en/workshop-registration
Location	Treviso, Italy
Date	20 September 2018
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	ECOBINDER project organized final public workshop to introduce project results at the end of the project. To present EnDurCrete project during the poster session with other H2020 projects under FENIX's portfolio.

Partner contribution	Brochures, roll up poster
Type of audience	Industry, scientific community, other H2020 projects Representatives.
Statistics	Approximately 30 participants
Attachments	

Event title	Circular hub: Circular economy in the construction sector
Website	https://incien.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/Program-akce-CE-ve-stavebnictvi%CC%81-2-1.pdf https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSes9IEuQxKCjdSE5tQVuxkt0_np8hg3pX5mzJfhUqSporITwA/
Location	Prague, Czech Republic
Date	20 September 2018
Type of event	Conference
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	RE ⁴ project (prefabricated concrete building components from CDW) in cooperation with Institute of Circular Economy and Business Innovation centre organized conference with afternoon workshops session on topic CE in construction sector. EnDurCrete project introduction via brochures.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Policy makers, ministry of environment, ministry of industry, academic community, other EU or national projects representatives, industry, associations, architects.
Statistics	More than 70 attendees
Attachments	

Event title	20th International Conference on Building Materials
Website	https://www.uni-weimar.de/de/bauingenieurwesen/institute/fib/ibausil/
Location	Weimar, Germany
Date	12-14 September 2018
Type of event	Conference
Responsible partner	HC
Event description	To present the project and its results. Headed by the Director of the F.A. Finger Institute for Building Materials Prof. Dr.-Ing. Horst-Michael Ludwig, the program of lectures focused on questions concerning the development of construction materials and their

	application. Focal points of the conference are traditionally: inorganic binders, concretes and durability of concretes.
Partner contribution	Presentation, conference proceedings
Type of audience	Companies, associations, universities
Statistics	about 600 participants
Attachments	

Event title	Deep renovation Joint Workshop (P2Endure project)
Website	https://www.p2endure-project.eu/ https://www.p2endure-project.eu/en/PublishingImages/SaveTheDate%20invitation.pdf
Location	Rome, Italy
Date	5 October 2018
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	RINA-C
Event description	The objective of the Workshop was to raise awareness on the most innovative building renovation and energy saving solutions and as well as to present and discuss altogether the main features of P2ENDURE e-Marketplace. The workshop brought together stakeholders representing key decision makers and implementers in the field of deep renovation of buildings, along with retrofitting solutions users, and developers for an array of interactive poster sessions and discussions, and a unique hands-on showcase of innovative deep renovation of building solutions.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Scientific community, industry, universities, policy makers, EU projects representatives.
Statistics	About 70 attendees
Attachments	

P2ENDURE

Deep renovation Joint Workshop

P2ENDURE TCP Workshop

Save the Date!

Mark your calendar for the Deep renovation Joint Workshop

**5 October 2018 at Hotel Cardinal St Peter
Leone Dehon, 71 - 00165
Rome, Italy**

The Deep renovation Joint Workshop is set for **5 October 2018**

Don't miss the opportunity for an inside look at most innovative systems for deep renovation of building envelopes and technical systems

The event is hosted by P2ENDURE project and is organised in conjunction with EENSULATE and ENVISION projects

P2ENDURE aims at improving the availability and performance of energy saving solutions for deep renovation and transformation of vacant, obsolete or sub-optimal public buildings into dwellings.

The project provides Plug & Play solutions which are ready to implement, affordable, 50% faster from production to on-site assembly, scalable and adaptable (in all European countries).

P2ENDURE (PLUG-AND-PLAY PRODUCT AND PROCESS INNOVATION FOR ENERGY-EFFICIENT BUILDING DEEP RENOVATION) has received funding from the European Union's Programme H2020-EE-2016-PPP under Grant Agreement no 72339 www.p2endure-project.eu

Event title	ECTP Conference
Website	http://infrastructure.ectp.org/news-events/news/news-detail/next-ectp-conference-planned-14-november-2018-save-the-date/
Location	Brussels, Belgium
Date	13-14 November 2018
Type of event	Conference
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	To disseminate the project via booth exposition together with other H2020 projects, to discuss with conference participants project development, possible synergies.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Scientific community, industry, other EU projects, policy makers, ECTP members, Project officers.
Statistics	About 300 participants

Attachments

Event title	ANDAF conference
Website	N/A
Location	Padova, Italy
Date	25 February 2019
Type of event	Conference
Responsible partner	FENIX

Event description	The conference focused on financing options for various stakeholders and industries. EnDurCrete project introduced during the FENIX company presentation as one of the projects in portfolio.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Industry representatives.
Statistics	About 40 participants
Attachments	

Event title	“TODAY’S WASTE, TOMORROW MATERIAL” – Circular Economy in Construction
Website	https://www.wsed.at/en/programme/innovation-workshops-energy-and-buildings.html
Location	Wels, Austria
Date	28 February 2019
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	FENIX

Event description	Workshop co-organized by cluster projects (FISSAC, VEEP, INNOWEE, GREENINSTRUCT) within the WSED conference. EnDurCrete project presented via brochures and roll up poster.
Partner contribution	Brochures, roll up poster
Type of audience	Other H2020 projects representatives, participant of the WSED confer
Statistics	25 attendees

Attachments

Workshop is organized within the World Sustainable Energy Days, session "Innovation Workshops Energy and Buildings"

Five H2020 research and innovation projects are pleased to invite researchers, industrial companies, professionals and wide public interested in the topic of circular economy for the common workshop called "Today's waste, tomorrow material". Projects representatives will introduce their results and lead interactive discussions related to the topic. The event will be held in English.

Workshop registration is free of charge, but it is necessary to be registered on the WSED conference in order to participate in the workshop.

Workshop registration for free: <https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/today-s-waste-tomorrow-material-circular-economy-in-construction-tickets-520495899>

Contact person: Petra Colantonio, petra.colantonio@fenix.tn.cz

The projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Follow WSED and our projects online to be posted with the latest news.

14:00 - 14:05	Event opening and welcome	Barbara Blaskovicova, FENIX TNT, Czech Republic
Projects Introduction		
14:05 - 14:15	RE4 - Reuse and recycling of CW materials and structures in energy efficient prefabricated elements	Linus Brander, RE4, Sweden
14:15 - 14:25	VEEP - Get effective recycling of CW in high added value energy efficient prefabricated concrete components	Anna Paraboschi, RNA Consulting, Italy
14:25 - 14:35	GREENINSTRUCT - Prefabrication for refurbishment from a modular perspective by way of a universal building block with customization potential	Gediminas Kasiukas, Brunel University London, UK
14:35 - 14:45	INNOWEE - Development of new economic fly viable, flexible and modular solutions able to process high amounts of CW waste and reaching at the same time high performance in terms of energy efficiency and environmental impact	Adriana Bernardi, CNR-IRAC, Italy
14:45 - 14:55	FISSAC - Fostering industrial symbiosis for a sustainable resource intensive industry across the extend of construction value chain	Giorgio Urbano, RNA Consulting, Italy
14:55 - 15:15	Coffee break	
Interactive poster sessions		
15:15 - 15:30	RE4 project	Michael Scullin, CDE Global, UK
15:30 - 15:45	VEEP project	Anna Paraboschi, RNA Consulting, Italy
15:45 - 16:00	GREENINSTRUCT project	Ines Kantsauer, ALCHEMIA-NOVA, Austria
16:00 - 16:15	INNOWEE project	Anja Lesek/Sabina Kramar, ZAG, Slovenia
16:15 - 16:30	FISSAC project	Giorgio Urbano, RNA Consulting, Italy
16:35 - 16:55	Panel discussion with speakers	

Event title	AMANAC workshop of EuroNanoForum 2019
Website	https://www.euronanoforum2019.eu/
Location	Bucharest, Romania
Date	14 June 2019
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	RINA-C
Event description	This workshop will be organized within the EuroNanoForum 2019, an event of the Romanian Presidency of the Council of the European Union, stands as the most significant European forum that brings together scientists, industrialists and policy makers. The event is anticipating approx. 1000 participants from Europe and across the globe and offers opportunities for discussions on cross-sectorial challenges focusing on both the industrial application of research results and future strategic research priorities in the area of Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials of the Horizon 2020 NMBP Programme and beyond.
Partner contribution	Presentation, brochures

Type of audience	Scientists, industrialists and policy makers
Statistics	app. 1000 participants expected
Attachments	

Event title	Workshop "TRANSFORMING CONSTRUCTION WASTE INTO ENERGY EFFICIENT SOLUTIONS"
Website	https://eusew.eu/transforming-construction-waste-energy-efficient-solutions?fbclid=IwAR0XxOwU2K_RYVSedgLfKtZPqSjK5urozlnVKVdDfcvPSAQXF8BWgD72RB4
Location	Brussels, Belgium
Date	18 June 2019
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	Workshop "TRANSFORMING CONSTRUCTION WASTE INTO ENERGY EFFICIENT SOLUTIONS" organized by RE4, VEEP, INNOWEE and GREEN INSTRUCT projects during the EUSEW. EnDurCrete project presented via booth with brochures.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Industry representatives, H2020 projects representative, project officers
Statistics	app. 50 participants

Attachments

Event title	Conference "XII Convegno Nazionale INSTM - XV Convegno Nazionale AIMAT "GET-TOGETHER CONFERENCE ON MATERIALS"
Website	http://www.instm.it/convegno_nazionale_instm_aimat.aspx
Location	Ischia Porto, Italy
Date	23 July 2019
Type of event	National Conference
Responsible partner	UNIVPM
Event description	Presentation "Carbon-based fillers and fibres for electrically conductive cement mortars" discussed by Alessandra Mobili and related abstract
Partner contribution	Presentation of UNIVPM activity within EnDurCrete project
Type of audience	Academic researchers
Statistics	app. 50 participants

<p>Attachments</p>	

Event title	Meeting with international clients
Website	N/A
Location	Casale sul Sile, Italy
Date	17th October 2019
Type of event	Business meeting
Responsible partner	NTESI
Event description	Nuova Tesisystem organized a meeting with foreign construction companies from USA, Canada, China, Emirates, Bangladesh, Serbia, Latvia, Estonia. And took the opportunity to make known, in addition to the company and to disseminate the research project ENDURCRETE in which they participate.

Partner contribution	Presentation, brochures
Type of audience	Industry representatives
Statistics	About 30 participants

Event title	Economia circolare e sostenibilità per il settore delle costruzioni le esperienze del territorio in ambito europeo
Website	N/A
Location	Napoli, Italy
Date	21 October 2019
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	Event was organized by STRESS in cooperation with Unione Industriale Napoli. FENIX participated as a speaker for topic prefabricated concrete elements from CDW. EnDurCrete brochures available to the event participants.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Industry, association, other projects representatives.
Statistics	About 70 attendees

Attachments	
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NAPOLI 21 OTTOBRE 2019 Ore 16.00
Sala conferenze UNIONE INDUSTRIALI

ECONOMIA CIRCOLARE E SOSTENIBILITÀ PER IL SETTORE DELLE COSTRUZIONI

LE ESPERIENZE DEL TERRITORIO IN AMBITO EUROPEO

16.00 | Saluti

VITO GRASSI | Presidente UNIONE INDUSTRIALI NAPOLI
EDOARDO COSENZA | Presidente ORDINE INGEGNERI NAPOLI
ENNIO RUBINO | Presidente STRESS Scari

16.30 | Presentazioni

Costruzioni sostenibili: soluzioni dalla ricerca europea per l'economia circolare

MARCO IJORIO | STRESS - *L'esperienza del Progetto Green Instruct*
PETRA COLANTONIO | FENIX - *L'esperienza del Progetto RE4*
DONATO ZANGANI | RINA Consulting - *L'esperienza del Progetto VEEP*

17.00 | Tavola rotonda

Sostenibilità, innovazione e crescita

Moderatore: MARIA CAVA | Giornalista

ENNIO RUBINO | Presidente STRESS Scari
EDOARDO ZANCHINI | Vice Presidente LegaAmbiente
SALVATORE RIONERO | Amministratore Delegato Tecnosistem SpA
FILIPPO DE ROSSI | Rettore dell'Università degli Studi del Sannio
FEDERICA BRANCACCIO | Presidente ACEN
RUDI GIRARDI | Vice Presidente ANCE
GAETANO MANFREDI* | Rettore dell'Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II

18.30 | Conclusioni

ANTONIO MARCHIELLO* | Assessore Ricerca e Attività produttive Regione Campania

* da confermare

Event title	Sustainable constructions: Solutions from Circular Economy
Website	http://www.re4.eu/re4---greeninstruct-workshop
Location	Bari, Italy
Date	24 October 2019
Type of event	Workshop
Responsible partner	FENIX
Event description	RE ⁴ project in cooperation with Greeninstruct project has organized a public workshop within the SAIE fair, various speakers from both projects have presented their results, discussed lessons learned, exchanged expertise and get the feedback from the SAIE fair participants. EnDurCrete project presented via brochures available to the workshop and SAIE participants.
Partner contribution	Brochures
Type of audience	Industry, academic, associations, other projects representatives.
Statistics	60 attendees signed, more passing by the stand.
Attachments	

Event title	Norsk Betongdag 2019 (Norwegian Concrete Day 2019)
Website	https://www.tekna.no/kursarkiv/norsk-betongdag-2019-38092/
Location	Trondheim, Norway
Date	22-24 October 2019
Type of event	Conference
Responsible partner	NTNU

Event description	Yearly meeting of the concrete industry in Norway with presentations on ongoing projects and challenges for the industry and research.
Partner contribution	Presentation: “Utvikling av en ny miljøvennlig komposittsement for framtidens bestandige betongkonstruksjoner – En statusoppdatering fra EnDurCrete-prosjektet” – «Development of a novel environmentally friendly composite cement for sustainable concrete structures in the future – An update from the EnDurCrete project»
Type of audience	Companies, associations, universities
Statistics	about 200 participants

Event title	Meeting with delegation of Polytechnic Milan
Website	N/A
Location	Casale sul Sile, Italy
Date	7 November 2019
Type of event	Meeting
Responsible partner	NTESI
Event description	Nuova Tesi System hosted at their plant a delegation of professor and post-graduates from the Polytechnic of Milan for a visit to the prefabrication plant. After a company presentation, NTESI took the opportunity to make known, in addition to the company and to disseminate the research project ENDURCRETE in which they participate.
Partner contribution	Brochures, poster design, videos
Type of audience	University professor, post-graduates
Statistics	20 visitors

Attachments	
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13.3 Other dissemination and communication activities

EnDurCrete project partners are promoting the project through their social media, website, newsletter, press releases, etc. The summary of all activities performed up to month M24 is shown in the table below and via graphs.

Figure 54: Graph of dissemination and communication activities for EnDurCrete project

Figure 55: Graph of EnDurCrete partners' activity in dissemination and communication activities

List of dissemination events and activities

Type of activity	Link	Event/activity title	Objective	Date	Place	Partner contribution	Countries addressed	Target audience and size	Partner/s
Social Media	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/endurcrete-h2020-kom-bruxelles-16th-january-2018-i-box-creates-1-/	EndurCrete H2020 - KoM Bruxelles (16th January 2018)	Inform on the EndurCrete KoM	16 January 2018	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Companies, associations, universities	IBOXC
Partner's Website	https://iboxcreate.es/i-box-h2020-endurcrete-inicio/	I-Box inicia "ENDURCRETE", proyecto financiado por el Programa I+D+i H2020 de la UE	Inform on the EndurCrete KoM	17 January 2018	IBOXC website	Note on partner's website	National	Companies, associations, universities	IBOXC
	https://iboxcreate.es/en/i-box-h2020-endurcrete-starting/	I-Box starts "ENDURCRETE", a project funded by the EU's R&D&i H2020 Program	Inform on the EndurCrete KoM	17 January 2018	IBOXC website	Note on partner's website	International	Companies, associations, universities	IBOXC
Press release	http://www.ectp.org/project-database-list/project-details/new-environmental-friendly-and-durable-concrete-integrating-industrial-by-products-and-hybrid-systems-for-civil-industrial-and-offshore-applications/	EnDurCrete - description of the project	Brief description of the project	March 2018	ECTP website	Press release	International	Professional public, scientific community, Policy makers, ECTP members, other EU funded projects, EC	FENIX
Partner's Website	http://www.acciona-construccion.com/es/innovacion/proyectos-de-innovacion/materiales/endurcrete/	ENDURCRETE. New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications	Brief description of the project on the ACCIONA Construction website - Spanish version	March 2018	ACCIONA website	Note on the partner's website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	ACCIONA

	http://www.acciona-construccion.com/innovati on/innovation-projects/materials/endurcrete/	ENDURCRETE. New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications	Brief description of the project on the ACCIONA Construction website - English version	March 2018	ACCIONA website	Note on the partner's website	International	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	ACCIONA
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/publications/endurcrete-project	EnDurCrete - description of the project	Brief description of the project	April 2019	EU Agenda	Press release	International	Professional public, Policy makers	FENIX
Partner's Website	https://iboxcreate.es/endurcrete-nuevo-hormigon-respetuoso-y-sostenible/	EnDurCrete: Nuevo Hormigón respetuoso con el medio ambiente y sostenible, integrando subproductos industriales y sistemas híbridos, para aplicaciones civiles, industriales y offshore	Inform about the development of EndurCrete	6th April 2018	IBOXC website	Note on the partner's website	National	Companies, associations, universities	IBOXC
Press release	https://iboxcreate.es/en/endurcrete-new-environmental-friendly-and-durable-concrete-integrating-industrial-by-products-and-hybrid-systems-for-civil-industrial-and-offshore-applications/	EnDurCrete: New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications	Inform about the development of EndurCrete	6th April 2018	IBOXC website	Note on the partner's website	International	Companies, associations, universities	IBOXC
Note on the website	https://eucyl.jcyl.es/web/jcyl/Eucyl/es/Plantilla100DetalleFeed/1277999678552/Noticia/1284801306160/Comunicacion	La Fundación Santa Bárbara acogerá pruebas de un prototipo de hormigón más duradero que desarrollan 12 países europeos en el marco del proyecto de investigación Endurcrete de la UE	Communication in the website of Junta of Castile and León	5 May 2018	website of Junta of Castile and León	Note on the website of Junta of Castile and León	National	Professional public, Policy makers	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project

Note on the website	http://www.europapress.es/castilla-y-leon/noticia-fundacion-santa-barbara-acogera-pruebas-prototipo-hormigon-mas-duradero-desarrollado-12-paises-europeos-20180506125941.html	La Fundación Santa Bárbara acogerá pruebas de un prototipo de hormigón más duradero desarrollado en 12 países europeos	Brief note on the website of the Europapress /Castilla y León	6 May 2018	website of the Europapress/ Castilla y León	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project
Note on the website	http://agencias.abc.es/agencias/noticia.asp?noticia=2810111	Doce países ensayarán en León un proyecto de UE para un hormigón más duradero	Inform about the project	6 May 2018	Brief note on the website of the ABC Agency	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project
Note on the website	https://www.lanuevacronica.com/la-fundacion-santa-barbara-acogera-las-pruebas-de-un-prototipo-de-hormigon-mas-duradero	La Fundación Santa Bárbara acogerá las pruebas de un prototipo de hormigón más duradero	Inform about the project	6 May 2018	Brief note on the website: LaNuevaCronica.com (Diario Leonés de información general - Newspaper of provincial circulation)	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project
Note on the website	http://www.leonoticias.com/comarcas/fundacion-santa-barbara-20180506113049-nt.html	La Fundación Santa Bárbara acogerá las pruebas un prototipo de hormigón más duradero para 12 países europeos	Inform about the project	6 May 2018	Brief note on the website of Leonoticias (Digital media)	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project
Note on the website	https://www.bembibredigital.com/bierzoalto/12160-la-fundacion-santa-barbara-acogera-pruebas-de-un-prototipo-de-hormigon-mas-duradero-que-desarrollan-12-paises-europeos-en-el-marco-del-proyecto-de-investigacion-endurcrete-de-la-ue	La Fundación Santa Bárbara acogerá pruebas de un prototipo de hormigón más duradero que desarrollan 12 países europeos en el marco del proyecto de investigación Endurcrete de la UE	Inform about the project	6 May 2018	Brief note on the website of Diario de Bembibre y Bierzo Alto (Digital media)	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project

Note on the website	https://www.efeverde.com/noticias/leon-proyecto-hormigon/	Doce países probarán en León un proyecto para un hormigón sostenible	Inform about the project	7 May 2018	Brief note on the website of the efe verde (Agencia EFE, S.A.)	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project
Note on the website	http://www.diariodeleon.es/noticias/bierzo/europa-probara-fundacion-santa-barbara-nuevo-prototipo-hormigon_1247089.html	Europa probará en la Fundación Santa Bárbara un nuevo prototipo de hormigón	Inform about the project	7 May 2018	Brief note on the website: Diario de León.es (Newspaper of provincial circulation)	Note on the website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	Fundación Santa Barbara - Company subcontracted by ACCIONA under ENDURCRETE project
Partner's website	http://www.accionaconstruccion.com/es/salaprensa/noticias/2018/mayo/accionaconstruccion-participa-proyecto-europeo-endurcrete/	ACCIONA Construcción participa en el proyecto europeo ENDURCRETE	Brief note on the press room of ACCIONA Construction website - Spanish version	9 May 2018	Acciona website	Note on the partner's website	National	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	ACCIONA
	http://www.accionaconstruccion.com/news/2018/may/acciona-construction-participates-european-endurcrete-project/	ACCIONA Construction participates in European ENDURCRETE project	Brief note on the press room of ACCIONA Construction website - English version	9 May 2018	Acciona website	Note on the partner's website	International	Companies, associations, universities, wide public	ACCIONA
Promo material release	http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/leaflets http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/posters http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/presentation	Endurcrete roll-up, brochure, presentation	Promo material design and release	June 2018 September 2018	Online	Brochure, Roll-up, Presentation	International	Scientific community, industry, universities, policy makers, wide public	FENIX
Website update - "Cluster projects" page	http://www.endurcrete.eu/cluster-projects	Cluster activity started. 2 projects identified as a suitable cluster - ReSHEALiance and ECO-Binder.	To foster cooperation between the projects dealing with the same topic.	September 2018	Online	EnDurCrete	International	Industry, scientific community, wide public, cluster projects	FENIX

E-newsletter	http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/newsletters	First newsletter in M12	To present the project and its results	January 2019	Online	Newsletter	International	Industry, scientific community, wide public, cluster projects	FENIX
Cluster activity	http://www.endurcrete.eu/cluster-projects	2 projects added to the "Cluster projects" page on the EnDurCrete website: DACOMAT, INNOVA Concrete	To foster cooperation between the projects dealing with the same topic.	January 2019	Online	Website	International	Industry, scientific community, wide public, cluster projects	FENIX
Social Media campaign	Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter	Project accounts	To present the project and its results	Created in January 2018, updated weekly	Online	Social network profiles Social network profiles creation and update	International	Scientific community, industry, universities, policy makers, wide public	FENIX
Graphic video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JYB90H5f8aY&t	EnDurCrete graphical video	To briefly present the project	March 2019	Online - Sharing through project website, partners channels, social media, during events	Video creation and promotion campaign	International	Scientific community, industry, universities, policy makers, wide public	FENIX
Partner's website	http://www.fenixtnt.cz/project/endurcrete	ENDURCRETE New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications	Note about the project on partner's website	April 2018	Online	Note on the partner's website	International	Industry, wide public	FENIX
Press release	http://www.buildup.eu/en/news/endurcrete-new-environmental-friendly-and-durable-concrete-integrating-industrial-products-and	EnDurCrete: New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications	To publish brief introduction about the project.	28 June 2018	BuildUp portal	Press release on portal online	International	BuildUp portal members	FENIX

e-newsletter	http://www.endurcrete.eu/files/Common%20newsletter_May%202019.pdf	NANOMATERIALS A SENSIBLE STRATEGY TOWARDS CONSTRUCTION SUSTAINABILITY	To design common newsletter with cluster projects (ReSHEALience and Lorcenis) about common events organized together (to download the ppts) and promote new events (AMANAC workshop) and introduce projects and their progress, to reach wider audience	June 2019	Online	Newsletter with cluster projects	International	Industry, scientific community, wide public, EU funded projects, newsletter subscribers, Sent to app. 200 addresses and shared on all possible communication channels	FENIX
Flyer for event organization	http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/leaflets	AMANAC WORKSHOP WHAT KIND OF BUILT ENVIRONMENT FOR FUTURE GENERATIONS?	To design promo flyer for the workshop organized by EnDurCrete and ReSHEALience projects.	June 2019	Online	Flyer	International	Industry, scientific community, wide public, EU funded projects, newsletter subscribers, Sent to app. 200 addresses and shared on all possible communication channels	FENIX/HC

Social media	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 2	To promote EnDurCrete newsletter	4 November 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX	
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2535717903325927?_xts=%5B0%5D=68.ARCUV_1p9UfuunuDip5CO0BntflpsYgSs5REpcslDWilAB_71sdcuXYciirXi07FxiLJ9IRlxQ2KToBiDiO0AZ3s_944DmfHhHc9T053FC3Rpol4uA3kUnESXDr9ZcE94TJaeN_JgKIAG8g2Bp8mSwlHOxxYgLS3mV9VtfQFDDrH_8pL5T-iOWdKcyT_f-dkE0JAYtbe5iSj-ZFBYLS6MlzY0nCcclbmxooYULmf4fjBRwJD1wNlosMKbfpkbFWHj2uhVQzc8aowHaNld2ihKliOD0705Kkrzk9EXx2VMBZ4YKpnV0Kj-bl75mNoFffiktNWB4Zu858y9cOEZ2RufecHM&_tn=-R									
Social media	EnDurCrete concrete samples	To promote EnDurCrete video	26 August 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX	

https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2475538012677250?_xts_%5B0%5D=68.ARDlxzJfBW-sAGbxOxhorhhw5pFOL4eOB0Lni5BptQFwcz14HkQA5WRLWf_r0BOHSVQBnZ1_RuQ9GuGXOPFM4dOA48W0aluDaB59Gbkzqz8GBq45K049Pz3ldX6LYHfxZ8LihvBTXuOaTsQ_9wbQPdQfWVNaLYKm1mFJC9fKt07i7KDCXefcNFOXukil3E6Z-xowgVr2QcE4Uij9mzX-pDAM_BDQH6EXiqGok8DFGT1heVa9vF24Vq6AMTL5WJR22Y6rUpBlftl4vkIN-iw9p5E5mZ_r8yYKD1fYxm3Hh6-2sbBYKqk73REK4dxhbieCav29fkZYLURKdRQL_1JWG&_tn_=-R								
Social media	EnDurCrete on Instagram	To promote EnDurCrete newly established Instagram profile	19 August 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2469704656593919?_xts_%5B0%5D=68.ARD8mAHwUca0Erl1n9Mctihs03ghpntnE4Xl1yxKdVt9S56CQ8FbswdeeQMV_jFF5DDEMOuVaC-YuajlmijwMcSL4p-YtwzH2qKdeKz413FA6aleAptTcmVVLva7AcUORVAWzujk35YK3uVcLUQbScu9Y8qpC3K6YUWv5t4scdfVvXlGCrSfiw57FB5g5i2hWoledQAI5T-aAXjilFCHAS71qX6MnGXJspY8LAnYEUt-GpXAXhJQG6bPK12ht8D5VbvCOHN92QaRbrF-AvcjdTtwiFsbx7QHwzL7it2mp4IDgV-P1ha-a9a7IIsII0Dha8PY00JkhFvxCP632oB1_P&_tn_=-R								
Social media	Meeting among Nuova Tesi, FENIX and UNIVPM in Casale sul Site Nuova Tesi's laboratory, filming of the concrete samples	To share project update, photos from the meeting	5 August 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2459737204257331?_xts_%5B0%5D=68.ARAeB8F-dysHalDo2Eqr8rCmsM--C0v2s5e0vysbMEDQAr4vtic-A_y_FDAwmqroD5xB96gVou1lwKpmtA5hdppVsSgHL4-jv4pzs4d8CLGWRWVfRc0oLO_550q1VckYkN2JM-zWFZB52mmpfDFZPtDacWCvg7cWfW_tp98KqYdpYO2H0xKk16Qu_daEWU-ua2pDJdhfPgPj91h94uBCPNifif-KB80iS4ULWpFiigz4h7PI8qnLi_tiwyf37yUBvZK0TuQJrVvW_YElht3zg_lppkK2VXPDOEqWFMFo2Sv8wHn1t49EWGIN6M7E9u1XIFHf3_HKfz-94p13EP8BwScvLLH0GA1OWURLcw28L20Y01CrI6k6bIEHtzt1yKWzhzBsAGEXNu-1dbnYVUEBjBinEB9Ha7MmkPOVupeV_nQEbihvGqGRHxluj_RWep05Abvztggo4_1kvgm26CkV_5cWwZL0ghwc3PiqwhUz3rcev5kk63T-K2JZID-D5&_tn_=-R								
Social media	Working on vacation?	Promoting one of the EnDurCrete demo site - Krk bridge in Croatia from the plane view	26 July 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/photos/a.1535664493331278/2452501568314228/?type=3&theater								
Social media	EU Web Awards 2019	Promoting EnDurCrete website for the EU Web Award	24 July 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/photos/a.1535664493331278/2428500714047647/?type=3&theater								
Social media	Joint newsletter EnDurCrete+Reshealience+Lorcenis project	Promoting the common newsletter as a summary after the events organized together	13 June 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2419717338259318?_xts_%5B0%5D=68.ARCJQLnJGzek2_e6j7rP7Hd-0_4En0xLEeoGhmpSGOiuZuSG0MaovayM8MO0v04UVNw-GtnYvptGuVo7FDw0OptfLWCKbkvQ2gFWS0U7TgXTI1Ch7KzCij413fHgv64-YXG5YkxGjQ18GH8HTD7x3pbx-AMWzkiEhwheB5-k7v4UHk9fctEMR_wuwlK0mlbX--Rw3c8SmR_RU5Xm7y6uXY3vYManimDaPEogv8Un9SrWKyrHEv2bVlmp1XV1K2Yalp1AJT1v1AmU9B5E_0-1wPW0tZgNRZ_ebpiwBYAVT93I0vEAp2WbNcHWQeFBK3-iCeTrNsDZPiV0xHKbojITXqXR&_tn_=-R								
Social media	New EnDurCrete video	Promoting EnDurCrete graphical video	25 April 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2383470548550664?_xts_%5B0%5D=68.ARABQtJefU9aMwWH3NQhquUXCzNuc-doM022EqA3Jq_cgwkdl-31l3iuU_NERqolb6xq5rKZWhvcADzoxhGOa4BlooV8ljXgAEPFHHiwN-baHOUGGXsA264LxDRqV_KzwLRqWwWiuUeLIMfZhil_tTYO-qu3BXQ_MXByYwVdQADpHvRWikaLNGzvZbDpy32Kjh_63GCTXeE54qiBEHFWJ-TLFKOUSsJN_faLwKHbUSkyfSudbflLhYhDWgxMggvfIbcX20C13Pvf_RI_NCV8r89QEZ11bUkhvZsIxhXhRMA95YgSHJewc7dJaSb6w-EleDTHwCudKk0oLFL1ECf0xP-j9C1&_tn_=-R								

Social media	Register to AMANAC workshop Brussels	Promoting the AMANAC workshop	17 April 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX	
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/photos/a.1535664493331278/2378440152387037/?type=3&theater									
Social media	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 1	To promote EnDurCrete newsletter	4 February 2019	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX	
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2331302840434102?__xts__%5B0%5D=68.ARBtc9UxopzMdPGpuRrynm0Y7cfjuRuVQoTc4vqk8uug-V9MAkhXnwftD5MgfrSBXhN3cyCw7kuQB3vLqzgXpOcczanuSuCJVH8vvMG9LyGh04EK9FRExv39qcZ5nit0ktT1Kj8tWrwFoHvSg3FKSi3dZzx5UI-Uh7k0mb7n9lGmpacftvNISEDJjmuEj5YfR5u6_Zt4vZV_4J9yGR88x_SgZ91_GUpasfMMpFwXKNqUf73Qqf3X85MR50ZYAXhFFjPkygYu5LaQwFPfinT0W8G9IzfbX-0o5zGfcU1mqfrscckV0BuMjBhpkawVVe6S01cQf0CqGiklEdsj5shd40HxrfZj936HbZv3uFbQ8kPTvi00hcSmOyinTnL1EP_Fh80MMd80RjSkgs3TFQWGHGDSH1h2uhzEC1VY-qW8jc77y9SmF3IWUkCtIzn8RcCyKJFX7cijO7F3rIFitAYskGf052tAS1rtMZWzxDEWbWukq8w5AQopPG&__tn__=-R									
Social media	Register to AMANAC workshop Vienna	Promoting the AMANAC workshop	25 October 2018	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX	
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2261478004083253?__xts__%5B0%5D=68.ARB2uzCU9_WW2v3IAoDioDem4eaWg4Z_e9Tvd_L0N4u0io-71aiYAbag-M_bqjCN9sLcAdoPu8aBhtzicNg3xiOSdXT8eAjzK5uijEbAHzKghRvcVgRYtMPm-VmHtISGIRWmQrSj9yYf0mZV3gHWc_SE3KEQF5TkGxqWaBDdMfalQ83zV6UkoehKafxHISY5VkhPp_gg1fUnt86gMAiGco4QwM4HpxhyzdRpm5_M4sXCclnRB35OMqnOgGQ06sWFz-J4eVXVE94cE82iFY3g19M8ox-mbSilbIFA6OBOnzBHOcdsCXfod-K4fpMJQZ3DnD4yj0VGH-hiHirOdyPLICONnCN1_z5ZxI37RpMqng9RW36a2NP76i8q4jYx7BCINGssm37zRG5y1MqGDpai00gDmkU5Zod&__tn__=-R									
Social media	Meet us at INDTECH - AMANAC workshop	Promoting the AMANAC workshop	02 September 2018	Facebook	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX	
https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2232440196987034?__xts__%5B0%5D=68.ARAx0iGMXmLkFaNN9dA48XXklI9ynej-IP5q-skXQDlftf2OD-VmHtISGIRWmQrSj9yYf0mZV3gHWc_SE3KEQF5TkGxqWaBDdMfalQ83zV6UkoehKafxHISY5VkhPp_gg1fUnt86gMAiGco4QwM4HpxhyzdRpm5_M4sXCclnRB35OMqnOgGQ06sWFz-J4eVXVE94cE82iFY3g19M8ox-mbSilbIFA6OBOnzBHOcdsCXfod-K4fpMJQZ3DnD4yj0VGH-hiHirOdyPLICONnCN1_z5ZxI37RpMqng9RW36a2NP76i8q4jYx7BCINGssm37zRG5y1MqGDpai00gDmkU5Zod&__tn__=-R									
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6597097321249546241	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 2	To promote EnDurCrete newsletter	4 November 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6572008260130361344/	EnDurCrete concrete samples	To promote EnDurCrete video	26 August 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6569173074103672832/	EnDurCrete on Instagram	To promote EnDurCrete newly established Instagram profile	19 August 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6564113307450646528/	Meeting among Nuova Tesi, FENIX and UNIVPM in Casale sul Sile Nuova Tesi's laboratory, filming of the concrete samples	To share project update, photos from the meeting	5 August 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6560429470195560449	Working on vacation?	Promoting one of the EnDurCrete demo site - Krk bridge in Croatia from the plane view	26 July 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX

Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6548833827467468800/	EU Web Awards 2019	Promoting EnDurCrete website for the EU Web Award	24 July 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6527103271549702144/	New EnDurCrete video	Promoting EnDurCrete graphical video	25 April 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6498185029729030144/	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 1	To promote EnDurCrete newsletter	4 February 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/i/flow/consent_flow	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 2	To promote EnDurCrete newsletter	4 November 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1166243471482589185	EnDurCrete concrete samples	To promote EnDurCrete video	26 August 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1163408906598703104	EnDurCrete on Instagram	To promote EnDurCrete newly established Instagram profile	19 August 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1154665483171520512	Working on vacation?	Promoting one of the EnDurCrete demo site - Krk bridge in Croatia from the plane view	26 July 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1143069700080975873	EU Web Awards 2019	Promoting EnDurCrete website for the EU Web Award	24 July 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1139102297022185472	Joint newsletter EnDurCrete+Reshealience+Lorenis project	Promoting the common newsletter as a summary after the events organized together	13 June 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1121338166991048704	New EnDurCrete video	Promoting EnDurCrete graphical video	25 April 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1118773568710565888	Register to AMANAC workshop Brussels	Promoting the AMANAC workshop	17 April 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1092406611937845248	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 1	To promote EnDurCrete newsletter	4 February 2019	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX
Social media	https://twitter.com/FENIXNT1/status/1036505823814529024	Meet us at INDTECH - AMANAC workshop	Promoting the AMANAC workshop	02 September 2018	Twitter	Note on partner's social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	FENIX

Video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=35rdEJP82EU	EnDurCrete load tests on concrete panels video	Load tests on concrete panels in Nuova Tesi laboratory. First the stress test was carried out on the panel with traditional reinforcement and second on the panel reinforced with synthetic net.	October 2019	YouTube	Video published on YouTube channel	International	Industry, academic, wide public	NTESI
Video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=73vZn_aQlv8	EnDurCrete concrete samples video	Concrete panels production in Nuova Tesi laboratory, where the team from the Università Polytecnica delle Marche came to install sensors for measuring the electrical impedance of concrete. Four panels (50x50x10 cm) and a block (50x10x10 cm) were cast to perform the parametric analysis on the response of the self-sensing properties of concrete.	August 2019	YouTube	Video published on YouTube channel	International	Industry, academic, wide public	NTESI
Video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aF_Mkt_p3iq4	EnDurCrete concrete panels video	Sensorized concrete panels production in Nuova Tesi laboratory, including mechanical testing and textile reinforcement.	July 2019	YouTube	Video published on YouTube channel	International	Industry, academic, wide public	NTESI
e-newsletter	http://www.endurcrete.eu/documents/promo-material/newsletters	EnDurCrete project newsletter num. 2 release	To present the project progress and results	October 2019	Online	Newsletter	International	Industry, scientific community, wide public, cluster projects	FENIX
Press release	https://www.buildup.eu/en/news/endurcrete-project-new-video	EnDurCrete project video	To promote concrete samples video	September 2019	BuildUp portal	Press release on portal online	International	Industry, scientific community	FENIX
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/videos/35915	EnDurCrete promo video	To promote project video	July 2019	EU Agenda	Press release on portal online	International	Professional public, Policy makers	FENIX
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/videos/35936	EnDurCrete project concrete samples video	To promote project video	October 2019	EU Agenda	Press release on portal online	International	Professional public, Policy makers	FENIX
press release	https://euagenda.eu/videos/35937	EnDurCrete project load tests video	To promote project video	October 2019	EU Agenda	Press release on portal online	International	Professional public, Policy makers	FENIX

Social media	https://twitter.com/IBoxCreate/status/1019482392602570753	2nd Project Meeting	To promote project meeting	8 July 2018	Twitter	Note on partner' s social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	IBOXC
Social media	https://bit.ly/2OGtIit , https://bit.ly/2rsCUt6 https://bit.ly/2Dq57Gl	EndurCrete H2020 - KoM Bruxelles	To promote EnDurCrete project results.	16 January 2018	Facebook	Note on partner' s social media	National	Industry, academic, wide public	IBOXC
Social media	https://bit.ly/34pY1v6	The concrete specimens prepared together with ACCIONA	To promote EnDurCrete project results.	May 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner' s social media	National	Industry, academic, wide public	IBOXC
Social media	https://bit.ly/2pNZfB1	From IBOX we work together with the CIAC in the ENDURCRETE project where we scale our CORROLESS (Patented) product at an industrial level	To promote IBOX cooperation with CIAC in Endurcrete project on corroless products.	September 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner' s social media	National	Industry, academic, wide public	IBOXC
Social media	https://bit.ly/2qJFICm	EnDurCrete project on Twitter	CIAC sharing info about EnDurCrete project on Twitter.	July 2019	LinkedIn	Note on partner' s social media	International	Industry, academic, wide public	IBOXC

14 Conclusion

This deliverable D8.7 “Progress report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign” concludes the dissemination and communication strategy and activities performed for the EnDurCrete project during the last 24 months. Analysing the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which were set up at the beginning of the project, the EnDurCrete project is on a positive trend towards a successful achievement of the initial KPIs goal (for some activities the KIPs were already reached).

The main communication channel with the wide public is the project website, which is updated on regular basis with the latest project’s information in order to keep the viewer’s interest and update about the project results and technical development. Up to now the website has reached more than 14 500 views by 1 933 users and allowed more than 4 200 downloads of promo materials, public deliverables, newsletters, videos, publications, etc.

EnDurCrete project during the last 24 months designed 4 different promo materials (brochure, roll up poster, presentation, flyer for the AMANAC workshop), released 4 videos, established and weekly posted news on 4 social network profiles (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram), released 3 e-newsletters and 8 press releases on thematic portals. Project partners promoted the EnDurCrete project results during 6 conferences, 1 fair, 7 workshops, 1 brokerage event and 3 other types of dissemination event. The project has organized 3 public workshops, mainly in cooperation with cluster projects (ReSHEALience, Dacomat, Lorcenis). EnDurCrete published 4 articles in popularized magazines, 1 article in scientific journal, 2 bachelor thesis and 1 chapter in book.

Project partners are also promoting the project through their websites or social media. The most active project partners in dissemination and communication activities are FENIX, NUOVA TESI, HC, I-BOX, ACCIONA, RINA-C and UNIVPM.

Social media campaign is quite successful with more than 250 followers in total and nearly 60 000 impressions (how many people viewed the posts). e-Newsletter is released every six months and sent to subscribers and shared though EnDurCrete communication channels. The project is active also on thematic portals, such as BuildUp, ECTP, EU Agenda, where short press releases are posted on regular basis.

In the second half of the project the dissemination and communication activities will focus on the demosites and technical project results promotion, mainly focused on industry stakeholders, potential customers in the target sectors such as pre-cast and ready-mix concrete markets and manufacturers of new concrete technologies and end-users.

Special attention will be paid to the final public workshop organization close to the demo site and training activities such as e-Learning platform, videos, webinars and courses to support the training of individuals.